

Environmental Considerations in the Zero-waste Valorisation of Bauxite Residue: A Life Cycle Perspective

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Abstract

Bauxite residue, also known as red mud, is produced in large quantities as a result of alumina refining (the first stage in aluminium production), and is one of the world's most abundant and important industrial wastes. As demand for aluminium continues to increase and space to store this residue diminishes, the potential to utilise bauxite residue as a secondary resource is increasingly being considered by the alumina industry. Bauxite residue can be used as a source of iron, aluminium, titanium oxide, scandium and rare earth oxides, or utilised for its bulk properties to create cement clinkers or inorganic polymers. Achieving any of these uses however requires a series of complex valorisation processes, which in turn require inputs of energy and materials. Some bauxite residues also contain trace amounts of naturally occurring radionuclides.

The EU Horizon 2020 MSCA-ETN REDMUD project was set up to investigate the valorisation of bauxite residue in an integrated manner. The ultimate aim of the REDMUD project is to develop environmentally-friendly, zero-waste, integrated processes for extracting valuable materials from bauxite residue and/or utilising it at high volume. This thesis presents the environmental perspective on this aim, taking a life cycle view; that is, taking into account the upstream and downstream impacts, in addition to the direct impacts, which may result from diverting bauxite residue from landfill to the proposed valorisation processes. This involves using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approaches to understand the environmental balance between the impact avoided through landfill diversion and the substitution of conventional materials, and the impacts incurred by the use of materials and energy in the valorisation processes themselves. Importantly, the potential ionising radiation impact from naturally occurring radionuclides is also considered from a life cycle perspective for the first time.

A new life cycle impact assessment method for assessing the impacts of naturally occurring radionuclides was developed. In addition, two pieces of research software, designed to overcome the current shortcomings in LCA software with respect to streamlined and prospective LCA studies of emerging technologies are presented as part of this thesis.

The potential hotspots of environmental impact in a single step valorisation process, the production of high bauxite residue content inorganic polymers, were identified. The results identify the high

temperature processing of bauxite residue, in order to transform it into a reactive precursor capable of forming solid inorganic polymers, as a hotspot of environmental impact across a range of environmental impact measures. The production of alkaline activating solutions (the other reagent in the polymerisation reaction) also represented a hotspot of environmental impact. These hotspots were used to identify possible future research directions for this process, which have the potential to reduce the environmental impact of this valorisation process.

Finally it was shown that even in the absence of a detailed and quantified system description, qualitative approaches based on life cycle thinking can be usefully applied to identify important aspects on both sides of the environmental balance between the impacts avoided and the impacts incurred in waste valorisation. Chemical reaction products, chemical synthesis, thermal and mechanical energy are highlighted as potential sources of environmental impact. A case study, looking at the combined extraction of iron and production of inorganic polymers from bauxite residue was used to demonstrate the validity of these qualitative approaches. This study also demonstrated that combining the extraction of iron and inorganic polymers is vital in order to yield a net environmental benefit in terms of climate change.

This thesis provides an initial step on the road towards the environmentally sustainable valorisation of bauxite residue, as well as the analytical tools and additional impact assessment measures required to ensure that this journey can be continued, both within the REDMUD project and beyond.

Keywords

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), bauxite residue, waste valorisation, Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM), Life Cycle Thinking, LCA software, Circular Economy

Sammanfattning

Bauxitrester, även känt som *rödslam*, eller *bauxitslam* (*eng: red mud*), produceras i stora mängder vid förädling av bauxit till aluminiumoxid och är ett av världens mest rikligt förekommande och viktiga industriella avfall. Eftersom efterfrågan på aluminium fortsätter att öka och utrymme för att lagra detta avfall blir allt mer begränsat, överväger industrin alltmer möjligheten att utnyttja bauxitrester som en sekundär resurs. Bauxitrester kan användas som en källa till utvinning av järn, aluminium, titanoxid, scandium- och sällsynta jordartsmetalloxider eller utnyttjas för dess bulkegenskaper för att tillverka cementklinkers eller geopolymerer (*eng: inorganic polymers*). För att uppnå något av dessa användningsområden krävs emellertid en rad komplexa valoriseringsprocesser, som i sin tur kräver användning av energi och material. Vissa bauxitrester innehåller också spårmängder av naturligt förekommande radionuklider.

EU:s Horizon 2020 MSCA-ETN REDMUD-projekt inrättades för att undersöka möjligheter för valorisering av bauxitrester på ett integrerat sätt. Det slutgiltiga målet med REDMUD-projektet är att utveckla miljövänliga, avfallsfria, integrerade processer för att extrahera värdefulla material från bauxitrester och/eller utnyttja det i stora volymer. Avhandlingen behandlar detta syfte ur miljösynpunkt och med ett livscykelperspektiv; det vill säga med hänsyn till den uppströms- och nedströms miljöpåverkan som, utöver de direkta effekterna, kan uppstå då bauxitrester flyttas från deponi till de föreslagna valoriseringsprocesserna. Det innebär att man använder Livscykelanalys (LCA) för att förstå balansen mellan å ena sidan miljöpåverkan som undviks genom minskad deponering och substitution av konventionella material och å andra sidan den ytterligare miljöpåverkan som användningen av material och energi i valoriseringsprocesserna medför. Det är viktigt att den potentiella joniserande strålningseffekten från naturligt förekommande radionuklider också bedöms från ett livscykelperspektiv för första gången.

En ny metod för miljöpåverkansbedömning i LCA av effekterna av naturligt förekommande radionuklider har utvecklats. Dessutom presenteras två nyutvecklade mjukvaror för LCA forskning, utformade för att övervinna de nuvarande begränsningarna i tillgänglig LCA-mjukvara med avseende på förenklad och

framåtblickande LCA-studier av framväxande teknologier som en del av denna avhandling.

Potentiella miljömässiga hotspots i en enstegs valoriseringsprocess, produktion av geopolimerer med hög andel bauxitrest, identifierades. Resultaten visar att högtemperaturbehandling av bauxitrest, för att omvandla dessa till en reaktiv prekursor som kan bilda fasta geopolimerer, är en hotspot för en rada olika kategorier av miljöpåverkan. Produktionen av alkalisk aktivator (*eng: alkaline activating solution*) (det andra reagenset i polymerisationsreaktionen) utgjorde också en hotspot av miljöpåverkan. Dessa hotspots användes för att identifiera möjliga framtida forskningsvägar för denna process, som har potential att minska miljöpåverkan av denna valoriseringsprocess.

Slutligen visades att även om det saknas en detaljerad och kvantifierad systembeskrivning kan kvalitativa tillvägagångssätt baserat på livscykel tänkande med fördel användas för att identifiera viktiga aspekter på båda sidor av balansen mellan den miljöpåverkan som undviks och den som uppstår vid avfallsvalorisering. Kemiska reaktionsprodukter, kemisk syntes, termisk och mekanisk energi lyfts fram som potentiella källor till miljöpåverkan. En fallstudie av den kombinerade utvinningen av järn och produktion av geopolimerer från bauxitrest användes för att visa giltigheten av dessa kvalitativa metoder. Denna studie visade också att en kombination av utvinning av järn och tillverkning av geopolimerer är avgörande för att ge en netto miljönytta med avseende på klimatpåverkan.

Denna avhandling redogör för ett första steg på vägen mot en miljömässigt hållbar valorisering av bauxitrest, samt de analytiska verktygen och de ytterligare metoder för miljöpåverkansbedömning som krävs för att säkerställa att denna utveckling kan fortsätta, både inom REDMUD-projektet och bortom det.

Nyckelord

Livscykelanalys (LCA), bauxitrest, avfallsvalorisering, naturligt förekommande radioaktiva ämnen (NORM), livscykel tänkande, LCA-programvara, cirkulär ekonomi

Preface

My personal journey into the world of bauxite residue valorisation began at the check-in area of Düsseldorf airport, halfway through a rather circuitous, pre-Christmas journey from Leuven to Uppsala. I had finally reached a reliable WiFi connection and could check my emails. The interview in Leuven had been successful, and I was the freshly minted ‘ESR14’ for the EU Horizon 2010 MSCA-ETN REDMUD project. The work presented in this PhD thesis represents the culmination of my efforts in this role.

The ETN-REDMUD project is a European Training Network, consisting of 15 Early Stage Researchers (ESRs), each working towards their PhD, at nine different academic and industrial institutions around the EU. The overall aim of the REDMUD project is to *‘develop zero-waste, environmentally-friendly recycling flow sheets for both fresh and previously stockpiled bauxite residues’*.

The first four of these ESRs are aiming to find ways to extract iron and aluminium from bauxite residue, ESRs 5 to 11 are trying to extract trace metals; titanium, scandium and rare earth elements; from bauxite residue by various traditional (selective leaching and precipitation) and non-traditional (ion-exchange, ionic liquid solvation, supported ionic liquids) means. ESRs 11 and 12 were tasked with finding high volume applications of bauxite residue in cements and inorganic polymer binders respectively.

ESR 13 had the challenge of determining the behaviour of commercially and environmentally important trace metals within the Bayer process, while ESR15 was responsible for understanding the potential radiological consequences from the naturally occurring radioactive materials contained within bauxite residue when it is utilised in valorisation processes.

My role, as ESR14, was to provide the environmental perspective on the valorisation technologies being developed within the project, from a life cycle perspective.

As all of the PhDs began at around the same time, the first element of my role was to work with ESR15 (Andrei Goronovski) to understand the potential for radiological impact to result from the life cycle of the bauxite residue valorisation technologies, and, if appropriate, develop a suitable Life Cycle Impact Assessment method to account for this impact. This led to Papers I and II.

As the project developed, and the technologies being developed by ESRs 1-12 began to take shape, enough data became available to

undertake streamlined assessments and identify potential hotspots of impact. The most detailed and comprehensive of these studies was carried out in collaboration with ESR12 (Tobias Hertel) on the creation of inorganic polymers, as presented in Paper V of this thesis. I also carried out high level LCA assessments of iron and aluminium extraction, dissolution of rare earths with ionic liquids, and cement production from bauxite residue.

It became clear during the modelling for these assessments that the traditional LCA software (SimaPro) was not an ideal fit for the types of fully parameterised foreground models that were the natural consequence of the data produced by the other ESRs. It also became clear, after the delivery of a brief SimaPro training course at a network meeting in Stockholm, that if there was to be any chance of the ESRs carrying out their own assessments, a more user friendly software package would be needed. My, initially separate, solutions to these two problems coalesced to create the *lcopt* software package (Paper III). *Lcopt-cv* (Paper IV) grew out of the potential applications of *lcopt* in LCA teaching, particularly to process engineers, in part due to the enthusiasm and ease with which the other ESRs were able to draw useful flow diagrams of their processes.

As the REDMUD project drew to a close, there was a concerted effort by the other ESRs to provide me with representative flow diagrams of their individual, and in some cases combined, processes. These formed the basis for the qualitative analysis in Paper VI. As such, Paper VI represents a synthesis of the most important environmental aspects with respect to the future, environmentally-friendly valorisation of bauxite residue, and a fitting summary of my role within the REDMUD project.

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I would like to express my heartfelt thanks to all of the people who have made this thesis possible.

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I would also like to say a big thank you to the three members of our advisory board – Ken Evans, Katy Tsemelis and Gyorgy Banvolgyi. Your knowledge and insights into the alumina sector and bauxite residue were invaluable to me, and your patience and thorough answers to my, often seemingly basic, questions were very much appreciated.

My time in the REDMUD project was punctuated by two secondments, one to Estonia and one to Greece. I would like to say thank you to Dr. Alan Tkaczyk and Andrei Goronovski for their help and support during my time in Estonia, and to Dr. Vicky Vassiliadou, Prof. Dimitris Pnias, and the four Greece based ESRs, Chiara Cardenia, Pritii Tam, Chiara Bonomi and Johannes Vind for helping arrange my secondment and making me feel welcome in Greece.

All of the ESRs in the REDMUD project deserve special thanks. It was a fantastic experience working with all of you. Buhle, Chiara (C), Stergi, Pritii, Gödze, Chiara (B), Rodolfo, Dzenita, Wenzhong, Bengi, David, Tobi, Johannes and Andrei: thank you! I'd like to think that we have become friends as well as colleagues and I look forward to seeing you, and potentially collaborating with you again in the future. Thank you Andrei and Tobi, my ESR co-authors, in particular for all of your hard work on the papers that are in this thesis.

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I am extraordinarily grateful to my main supervisor, Anna Björklund. Thank you for your patience and flexibility with my frequent ‘otherwise located-ness’, and for allowing me the intellectual freedom to develop my PhD project into something I feel very proud to call my own. Your support from day one has been fantastic, and I never had any doubts that our work together would be anything but a success. I hope the research contained here lives up to your expectations!

I would also like to thank my co-supervisors Göran Finnveden and Karel van Acker. Your input and insights throughout my PhD have been invaluable, and are very much appreciated.

I would like to thank all of my co-authors; Andrei Goronovski, Alan Tkaczyk, Tobias Hertel, Yiannis Pontikes, Anna Björklund and Göran Finnveden. It was a pleasure working with you, and all of your contributions were very much appreciated.

To my family, thank you for your endless love, encouragement and support, throughout my PhD in particular, but also throughout my whole life to this point.

Lastly, and most importantly, thank you to my wonderful wife Claire. Thank you for all of the support you’ve given me, for putting up with my extended absences, and particularly for being so understanding when I accidentally emigrated to Estonia without telling you... I couldn’t have done this without you, and I am eternally grateful. And Rosie – you may only have joined us for the last few months of Daddy’s PhD, but rest assured you more than repaid all of the challenges associated with lack of sleep with the moments of joy and the motivation offered by your little smile whenever I needed a break from writing. It will be a few years before you’re able to read this dedication (and probably a few more before I make you read the whole thesis...) but you should know that you were a great help!

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This publication reflects only the authors’ view, exempting the Community from any liability. Project website: <http://www.etn.redmud.org>

List of appended papers

Paper I

Joyce, P. J., Goronovski, A., Tkaczyk, A. H. and Björklund, A. (2017) 'A framework for including enhanced exposure to naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM) in LCA', *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 22(7), pp. 1078–1095. doi: 10.1007/s11367-016-1218-2.

Paper II

Goronovski, A., **Joyce, P. J.**, Björklund, A., Finnveden, G. and Tkaczyk, A. H. (2018) 'Impact assessment of enhanced exposure from Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM) within LCA', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, pp. 2824–2839. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.11.131.

Paper III

Joyce, P. J. (2017) 'Lcopt - An interactive tool for creating fully parameterised Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) foreground models', *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(16). doi: 10.21105/joss.00339.

Paper IV

Joyce P. J. (submitted) 'Computer vision for LCA foreground modelling - an initial pipeline and proof of concept software, lcopt-cv', *Manuscript submitted*

Paper V

Joyce, P. J., Hertel, T., Goronovski, A., Tkaczyk, A. H., Pontikes, Y. and Björklund, A. (2018) 'Identifying hotspots of environmental impact in the development of novel inorganic polymer paving blocks from bauxite residue', *Resources Conservation and Recycling*, 138, pp. 87-98. doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.07.006.

Paper VI

Joyce, P. J. and Björklund, A (submitted) 'Using Life Cycle Thinking to assess the sustainability benefits of complex valorization pathways for Bauxite Residue: the case of the MSCA-ETN REDMUD Project', *Manuscript submitted*

Contribution of the Author

Paper I: James Joyce is the first author of this article. James was responsible for devising the approach and the outline of the framework. The literature review was split between James Joyce and Andrei Goronovski. The final framework was put together in collaboration with Andrei Goronovski. James was responsible for the writing of the manuscript with input from co-authors.

Paper II: James Joyce is a joint first author of this article. James and Andrei Goronovski jointly developed the characterisation method. James devised and carried out the case study. Andrei Goronovski carried out the 'daughter radionuclides' sensitivity analysis, with James responsible for the remaining analyses. James was responsible for the structure of the article, and led the writing of the manuscript, with the exception of sections 3.1.5 and 5.2.1, which were written by Andrei Goronovski.

Paper III: James Joyce is the sole author of this article.

Paper IV: James Joyce is the sole author of this article.

Paper V: James Joyce is the first author of this article. James was responsible for devising the approach and undertaking the modelling and analysis. Tobias Hertel provided primary data for the production of bauxite residue derived inorganic polymers at lab scale, and text describing inorganic polymers and the previous research into the use of bauxite residue in these applications (incorporated into sections 2.1 and 2.2). Andrei Goronovski provided radiological analyses of polymer samples and developed the infrastructural extension to the NORM exposure LCIA model. James wrote the manuscript, with input and feedback from co-authors.

Paper VI: James Joyce is the first author of this article. James was responsible for collating flowsheets from other members of the REDMUD training network and combining them into an overall flowsheet. James carried out all analyses. James devised and wrote the manuscript, with input and feedback from Anna Björklund.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Bauxite residue, also known as red mud, is a by-product of the first stage of aluminium refining. It is one of the world's most important and abundant industrial wastes, with 150 million tonnes produced annually [1] and, extrapolating from 2010 figures¹ [2] to 2018, up to 4,000 million tonnes stockpiled. Only four million tonnes per year, less than 3% of the amount produced, is used productively [1]. The remainder needs to be disposed of, usually in some form of landfill.

Bauxite residue is generated as a result of the digestion of bauxite, the main ore of aluminium, via the Bayer process. The Bayer process was invented in the 1880's by Karl Josef Bayer. It is a hydrometallurgical process in which bauxite is leached at high pressure with concentrated sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to obtain a sodium aluminate solution [3]. Bauxite residue is the undissolved fraction of the bauxite which remains after leaching, and is separated from the sodium aluminate solution via a series of settling tanks [4].

The dissolved aluminium is precipitated from the sodium aluminate solution in the form of aluminium hydroxide ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$), which is calcined to produce alumina (aluminium oxide – Al_2O_3). This alumina is smelted to produce metallic aluminium [3].

The bauxite residue from the settling tanks takes the form of a sludge or slurry, usually at 20-30% solids content [4]. Bauxite residue is strongly alkaline ($\text{pH} > 11$) [2] and can, in some circumstances, contain concentrations of trace metals of regulatory concern [5]. Some bauxite residues also contain elevated levels of naturally occurring radionuclides (primarily ^{238}U and ^{232}Th , and their daughter nuclides) [6]. As such, proper management of this bauxite residue is a major concern for the alumina industry [1,2,7].

Before the 1980s, the most common way to manage bauxite residue was to store the slurry in lagoon-type impoundments created by dams or other earthworks. This included the damming of valleys or estuaries, or the filling of depleted mine or quarrying sites [1]. At this time, at least six alumina plants discharged the bauxite residue into the sea, and at some locations it was disposed of directly into rivers or estuaries [1].

¹ Estimated 3,000 million tonnes stockpiled in 2010. 150 million tonnes per year minus 4 million tonnes reused = 146 million tonnes per year = an additional 1168 million tonnes between 2010 and 2018.

From the mid-1980s onwards there has been a move away from these practices towards dry-stacking of bauxite residue [8]. Sea disposal was completely phased out by the end of 2015 [1]. Dry-stacking involves recovering more of the caustic leach liquor from the bauxite residue prior to disposal, commonly through filtration. This both increases the recovery of valuable caustic which can be reused in the Bayer process and decreases the risk of the high pH liquor leaking into the surrounding environment, while also reducing the space demands for bauxite residue disposal.

The need to move away from the lagooning of bauxite residue was thrown into sharp relief in October 2010 when a containment dam at a bauxite residue reservoir in Ajka, Hungary broke. The resulting disaster left 10 people dead and close to 150 injured while destroying practically all aquatic life in a section of a local river and leading to the pollution of over 400 hectares of land [9]. Regardless of improvements in the management of bauxite residue, current management practices are not sustainable in the long term. Indeed at one alumina refinery in Europe, the area allocated to landfilling bauxite residue will be full within the next 20 years (Aluminium of Greece, pers. comm.). As a result, much research and development effort is now focused on finding ways to use bauxite residue as a secondary resource.

There are a number of possible uses for bauxite residue which derive both from its composition and its mineralogical properties. The exact composition of bauxite residue depends on the types of bauxite used originally, and, to a certain extent, on the specific process conditions in the Bayer process [10]; however generalisations can be made (Figure 1). The main constituent of bauxite residue is iron oxide, typically at around 40 wt. % [11], in the form of haematite, goethite and magnetite. The second largest constituent is usually aluminium bearing minerals

Figure 1. Main constituents of bauxite residue (illustrative composition from [11])

not leached by the Bayer process. These can make up between 2 and 35% of bauxite residue [12], and include both minerals from the original bauxite which were incompletely digested and desilication products (DSP) – minerals containing aluminium, sodium and silicon produced via side reactions in the Bayer process.

In addition to these bulk metals, small amounts of titanium oxide (around 9%) [11] are present in bauxite residue, while valuable metals including scandium and rare earth elements are enriched in bauxite residue with respect to the original bauxite [13]. Some bauxite residues produced at refineries in Jamaica and Greece are sufficiently enriched in scandium that they have the potential to be used as secondary ores [14]. In addition to these useful metals however, bauxite residue is also commonly enriched in naturally occurring radionuclides (in particular ^{238}U and ^{232}Th and ^{40}K). As a result some bauxite residues are classed as Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM) [6].

Alongside the potentially valuable constituents of bauxite residue, its bulk properties mean that high volume reuse options also exist. These include use in high quantities in cements [15] or transformation into inorganic polymer building products [16].

The Horizon 2020 MSCA-ETN REDMUD project was set up to research new technologies both to extract valuable materials from bauxite residue and utilise it at high volume. It consists of 15 PhD researchers across nine institutions around the EU. Close collaboration between researchers within the project allows potential synergies between individual pathways to be identified, with the ultimate aim to create a set of zero-waste valorisation flow sheets, in which value is maximised and no residual waste remains. A key aim of the project is that the valorisation pathways which are developed should represent an environmental benefit over the current situation. The work presented in this thesis is in service of this aim.

Waste valorisation and recycling more broadly, have many potential environmental benefits. The use of recycled materials displaces the need for primary materials to be produced, therefore avoiding the environmental impacts associated with their extraction and processing. Diverting waste to recycling or valorisation systems also avoids any environmental burdens associated with waste treatment, for example the high land requirement and potentially caustic leachate associated with bauxite residue impoundment areas. An increasingly popular articulation of these benefits is the idea of the circular economy, where rather than being extracted, used and disposed of (as is commonly the case in the current so-called 'linear

economy'), materials, once extracted, are continuously cycled and re-cycled through the economy.

In order to assess whether recycling and valorisation systems are beneficial from an environmental perspective, it is important to take a life cycle approach. This means that both the upstream burdens associated with the production of materials and energy used in the treatment of the waste, and the avoided burdens associated with the displacement of materials and energy which occur as a result of recycling are taken into account, in addition to the direct burdens of the recycling system [17]. Generally speaking, recycling of a material leads to a lower total energy requirement and lower greenhouse gas emissions than incineration or landfilling of that same material [18]. This is particularly true for non-renewable materials, such as glass, metals and plastics. There are, however, exceptions. Recycling processes which yield high value products, but entail high energy requirements (e.g. feedstock recycling of plastics into high value chemical precursors) or the use of recycled materials to displace materials with a low environmental burden (e.g. displacing wood-derived products with recycled plastics) can both lead to situations where recycling is less environmentally favourable than incineration or landfilling [18].

It is therefore important to quantify and assess the net environmental effects of recycling and valorisation systems before making environmental claims. In many cases researchers dealing with the use of secondary resources make the implicit assumption that because waste and waste treatment is 'bad', any kind of reuse of this waste is therefore inherently 'good', without any further quantitative assessment e.g. [19,20].

It is also important to account for the potential environmental impacts across a broad and inclusive range of metrics, in order to avoid 'burden shifting'. Focusing on one (e.g. carbon footprint) or a small number of environmental impacts may mean that while a new technology outperforms the status quo on some metrics, a hidden burden may be accruing in a metric which is not currently measured. Idiomatically, there is a need to avoid 'robbing Peter to pay Paul'. In the case of bauxite residue, the possible presence of elevated levels ^{238}U and ^{232}Th mean that it is particularly important to be able to account for the potential enhanced exposure of humans and ecosystems to naturally occurring radionuclides as a result of valorisation to ensure that environmental benefits in terms of reduced emissions and resource extraction do not come at the cost of higher exposure to sources of ionising radiation.

1.2 Aim and scope of the thesis

The aim of this thesis is to contribute a life cycle perspective on the potential environmental impacts and benefits associated with the zero-waste valorisation of bauxite residue. This includes ensuring that the potential impacts resulting from elevated levels of natural radionuclides are assessed, to avoid 'burden shifting'; proposing modelling approaches to overcome the lack of industrial scale data of processes under development at lab scale, and; assessing the environmental impacts associated with both simple and more complex valorisation pathways for bauxite residue.

In order to fulfil this stated aim, the following specific research questions are addressed in this thesis:

RQ1. Integration of NORM exposure into LCA

Can, and should, the enhanced exposure to Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM) resulting from industrial processes, including the valorisation of bauxite residue, be integrated into the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework?

RQ2. LCA modelling approaches

What is the most suitable approach to modelling the industrial scale life cycle impacts of bauxite residue valorisation using lab scale data obtained in collaboration with non LCA experts?

RQ3. Single step valorisation of bauxite residue

What are the major life cycle environmental considerations in the creation of inorganic polymers from bauxite residue, a single step valorisation pathway?

RQ4. Multi-stage valorisation of bauxite residue

What additional life cycle considerations arise from more complex, multi-stage valorisation pathways for bauxite residue?

Each of these research questions is addressed in one or more of the appended papers which follow this introductory essay.

Table 1: Research questions addressed by each appended paper

#	Research Question	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
RQ 1.	Integration of NORM exposure into LCA	✓	✓			✓	
RQ 2.	LCA modelling approaches			✓	✓	✓	
RQ 3.	Assessment of single stage valorisation pathways					✓	
RQ 4.	Assessment of multi-stage valorisation pathways						✓

1.3 Outline of cover essay

This cover essay is a summary and a synthesis of the appended papers. This chapter (Chapter 1) provides the overall background to the thesis, the aim of the research and the research questions.

Chapter 2 provides more detailed scientific context to the research questions addressed, including the concept of zero-waste processing, the occurrence and potential dangers of NORM, and the *life cycle* approach taken to assess the environmental aspects of bauxite residue valorisation.

Chapter 3 provides a summary and an overview of the methods used in the papers.

Chapter 4 is a synthesis of the results of the research presented in the appended papers, in order to directly address the four research questions outlined above.

Chapter 5 discusses these results in a broader context, and highlights the contributions and limitations of this thesis.

Finally, Chapter 6 consists of the conclusions which can be drawn from this research, and potential directions for future work.

2 Scientific context

This chapter introduces some of the theoretical and scientific context for the themes explored in this thesis. This includes important concepts surrounding the quantification of environmental impacts from a life cycle perspective, the potential environmental issues surrounding ‘zero-waste’ processes, and the importance of naturally occurring radioactive materials with respect to bauxite residue valorisation.

2.1 Life cycle thinking

The environmental assessment of bauxite residue valorisation presented in this thesis has been carried out from a *life-cycle perspective*.

The life-cycle perspective is best exemplified by Life Cycle Thinking (LCT). LCT is a decision making paradigm in which the upstream and downstream consequences of an action are taken into account alongside the direct consequences [21]. Central to LCT is the concept that products have a life cycle, which begins with the extraction of materials from the environment and ends with their final disposal. Making changes at any point within this life cycle has consequences both at earlier points (upstream) and later points (downstream) in the life cycle.

For example, changing the material which a component of a product is made of, from steel to aluminium say, has an effect on the upstream life cycle – aluminium must now be produced instead of steel, and on the downstream life cycle – aluminium is less dense than steel, so requires less fuel to transport, and the waste treatment of the product will be affected by its new material composition.

The environmental aspects of LCT are underpinned by Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). LCA provides a standardised, quantified methodology to assess the potential life cycle environmental impact of products and services [22], and is the most important method used in this thesis (Section 3.2). LCA allows the environmental effect of the upstream and downstream changes to the life cycle of a system to be quantified, relative to a given *functional unit*. The use of a functional unit, describing the function the system provides rather than a specific material output, means that comparisons remain fair even if the function is delivered in a different way. This allows a net environmental effect to be calculated (to see whether the overall

effect of the change is positive or negative), across multiple categories of environmental impact. It also allows the areas of the life cycle in which the biggest changes in impact occur to be identified.

A major benefit of LCT, underpinned by LCA, is that it can be used to help avoid *burden shifting*. Generally, burden shifting is where reducing impacts in one area leads to an increase in impact elsewhere. Burdens may be shifted between impact categories (e.g. a reduction in GHG emissions, but an increase in ionising radiation exposure), between life cycle stages (e.g. a design change that leads to a decrease in impact in the production stage but an increase in the impact resulting from a product's disposal), or even between countries (e.g. through changes in the supply chain, or by shifting of burdens to a life cycle stage which mainly takes place elsewhere).

LCA can be used to identify potential burden shifting and propose solutions which result in an overall environmental benefit and an equitable distribution of environmental impacts and benefits. In this thesis, a life cycle approach is taken to ensure that when the flow sheets produced by the REDMUD project are said to be 'environmentally-friendly', this can be backed up by a rigorous and quantified scientific analysis.

2.2 Previous LCA studies of bauxite residue valorisation

LCA studies into the utilisation of bauxite residue as a resource are few and far between. While many options for its reuse have been proposed at lab scale, commercial scale applications of bauxite residue are scarce [1,23]. The resulting paucity of industrial scale data may be a factor in the lack of LCA studies available.

Two studies from Australia have quantified the benefits of utilising bauxite residue in relatively simple applications. Tuazon and Corder [23] present a comparative LCA of the use of seawater neutralised bauxite residue vs conventional quicklime for acid mine drainage remediation, taking into account net energy use, fuel consumption and carbon dioxide emissions. They show that despite the fact that the neutralisation capacity of the amended bauxite residue is lower than that of quicklime, therefore requiring more material to neutralise 1,000 m³ of acid drainage water and more fuel to transport this material, the electricity requirement and overall CO₂ emissions are lower when using amended bauxite residue as a neutralant. The main factor influencing the lower CO₂ emissions is the fact that substantial amounts of CO₂ are released to the environment in the production of quicklime as a result of the

decomposition of calcium carbonate in limestone to calcium oxide. This study demonstrates there are potential environmental benefits from low input, high volume reuse of bauxite residue, where the product displaced has a high environmental impact.

A second study by Biswas and Cooling [24] assessed the sustainability benefits of the displacement of virgin sand and crushed limestone with 'Red Sand', a product produced by Alcoa by washing and carbonating the coarse fraction of bauxite residue. The environmental savings they report, while appearing substantial on a superficial level (savings of 66,200 tonnes CO₂-eq over a 35 year period) do not stand up to scrutiny. This saving is based on assumed sales of 30 million tonnes of Red Sand, thus per tonne of Red Sand, just 2 kg CO₂-eq are saved. Although transportation is included in the Red Sand LCA, the climate change impact of as little as an additional 35 km of road transport over the virgin sand alternative would negate this benefit². This study shows that the environmental savings resulting from bauxite residue reuse can be marginal or even non-existent where the displaced material has a relatively low environmental impact.

Perhaps the assessment most closely aligned with the types of bauxite residue valorisation technologies considered in this thesis is the exergy analysis undertaken as part of the ENEXAL project of the coproduction of pig iron and mineral wool from bauxite residue, carried out at Aluminium of Greece [25]. The focus of this study was to understand the contribution of bauxite residue valorisation on the overall exergy efficiency of the Bayer process. The bauxite residue was sent to a pilot scale electric arc furnace (of proprietary design) where it underwent reductive smelting to produce pig iron and a glassy slag. This slag was then subsequently transformed into mineral wool. Incorporating this valorisation process increased the overall exergy efficiency of the alumina refinery by eight percentage points, from around 3% to over 11%, while producing two potentially valuable coproducts.

CO₂ emissions for both the original and augmented Bayer process were also calculated in this study and rose from 0.96 kg per kg of alumina produced to 3.68 kg; an increase of 2.72 kg CO₂. However, the augmented process also produced 0.189 kg of pig iron and 0.644 kg of mineral wool [25]. Calculating the potential

² The climate change impact of the transport of 1 tonne of material 1 km via a EURO6 >32 tonne lorry is approximately 0.068 kg CO₂-eq/tkm. Multiplied by 35 km, this is 2.4 kg CO₂-eq/t.

displacement of greenhouse gas emissions using this information³, an additional 1.15 kg CO₂-eq can be said to have been saved per kg of alumina produced. Subtracting this from the increase in CO₂ emissions however still results in a net increase of 1.56 kg CO₂-eq per kg alumina produced. This study demonstrates that while the exergy efficiency of the Bayer process can be substantially improved by the co-processing of bauxite residue into marketable products there is no guarantee that this will result in a net environmental benefit.

2.3 Waste and the ‘zero-waste’ ideal

2.3.1 *The waste hierarchy*

The exact wording of the aim of the MSCA-ETN REDMUD project is to ‘*develop zero-waste, environmentally-friendly recycling flow sheets for both fresh and previously stockpiled bauxite residues*’. An important aspect of this thesis is whether, in this context, ‘zero-waste’ and ‘environmentally-friendly’ are necessarily one and the same thing.

In the EU, the most important legislative aspects of waste and waste treatment are codified in the Waste Framework Directive [26]. Primary among these from the perspective of this thesis is the Waste Hierarchy (Article 4, paragraph 1). This provides a priority order for the prevention and management of waste for the best overall environmental outcome. At the top of the hierarchy are prevention and reuse – measures to avoid materials entering the waste management system. For waste entering the waste management system, recycling is the preferred option, followed by energy recovery. At the bottom of the waste hierarchy is landfill.

While the waste hierarchy provides a useful heuristic – moving up the waste hierarchy equals better environmental performance – there is always the potential for exceptions. Accordingly, paragraph 2 of Article 4 states that providing the best overall environmental outcome may require ‘specific waste streams departing from the hierarchy where this is justified by life-cycle thinking’. This nicely sums up the tension between progress towards zero-waste (moving up the waste hierarchy) and ensuring processes are environmentally- friendly, by applying life cycle thinking.

³ Using data from the ecoinvent database for the global market production of mineral wool and pig iron

2.3.2 *The true impact of waste – production*

In spite of its potential exceptions, the waste hierarchy is built on solid theoretical foundations. Waste represents a lack of efficiency, and increased resource efficiency has been identified as one of the most important contributors to sustainable development [27]. All materials utilised by human beings (items in the ‘technosphere’) were at some point extracted from the environment (the ‘biosphere’). Such extraction, and all subsequent transformation and processing requires energy and, commonly, other materials which in turn were extracted from the environment at some point in their life cycle. Material extraction and energy use are typically associated with impacts on the environment, for example through the transformation of land or the release of pollutants to air, water or soil.

Every material within the economy carries with it the upstream burden of all of the processes that were involved in its extraction and transformation up to that point. This burden is however balanced by the utility that material provides to the humans who are using it. When a material is wasted however, its utility is forfeited. In addition to the extra environmental burden incurred through waste treatment, the accrued burdens from the production of the material are borne by the environment and society for potentially no benefit.

Food waste is a particularly good example of this. Disposal of biodegradable waste in landfill can lead to the release of methane, a powerful greenhouse gas, to the environment as it degrades. Globally greenhouse gases amounting around 200 million tonnes of CO₂-eq are released as a result of the waste treatment of post-consumer food waste [28]. This is an environmental impact which can be directly attributed to wasting food. However, consider the fertilisers, pesticides and diesel required to cultivate this food, the fuel required to transport it, the electricity required to keep it cool, and the energy required to cook it. On average, the upstream burden of food in terms of greenhouse gas emissions outweighs the impact associated with its disposal by five times, resulting in annual greenhouse gas emissions equivalent to around one billion tonnes of CO₂ [28]. This impact was incurred for no utility benefit.

The waste hierarchy can thus be framed as a device for the maximising of the ratio of utility gained from a material vs. the accrued environmental burden associated with its life cycle. Preventing a material becoming a waste prolongs or ensures its

utility with no, or limited, additional environmental burden. Similarly, reuse prolongs utility at the cost of a small amount of environmental burden (associated with its reprocessing or relocation). Recycling allows utility to be prolonged, but the material produced is commonly of a lower quality ('downcycling') and hence a lower level of utility. Some level of additional environmental burden through the processing of the material is also incurred. Energy recovery is an attempt to salvage some additional utility from a material that would otherwise go to landfill, and is usually associated with environmental burdens associated with combustion. Finally, landfill is the point at which all potential utility is exhausted⁴.

2.3.3 *Paradigms for resource efficiency - Circular Economy and Industrial Ecology*

The acknowledgement that resource efficiency is a vital part of our continuing sustainable development has led to the conception of some potentially important new paradigms for how industry and society should function. Primary among these are the Circular Economy and Industrial Ecology. Both of these concepts take their inspiration from an idealised view of biological systems, where waste is said not to exist⁵. Rather, materials and nutrients are cycled through the system. Waste from one part of the ecosystem is used as a resource by another part.

The idea of the circular economy evolved and coalesced from a variety of inception points [29], including the cradle-to-cradle concept of McDonough and Braungart [30], the *limits to growth* thesis of the Club of Rome [31], and Kenneth Boulding's conception of *spaceship earth* [32]. It remains an eclectic concept with no fixed definition [33], but a version of the circular economy has achieved prominence in Europe in recent years, in part through its promotion by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation [33], and has been adopted by the EU as an aspiration for the next round of environmental legislation via the Circular Economy Action Plan [34].

In contrast to a *linear economy*, characterised by the *take-make-dispose* paradigm of the current economic system, a circular economy consists of technical and biological cycles in which

⁴ Although an emerging, but by no means mainstream, perspective holds that rather than constituting a final disposal option, landfills may represent temporary storage of materials prior to their later extraction via landfill mining [114].

⁵ Waste does exist in biological systems, limestone, coal, oil and gas are all well-known examples, but efficiency is generally far greater than that seen in industrial systems.

materials, or *nutrients*, should never become waste. Within such a circular economy, products are designed so that the durable materials (or *technical nutrients*) of which they are composed can be reused, and that the consumable materials (ideally composed only of *biological nutrients*) can be safely returned to the biosphere to re-enter biological cycles [35]. In theory, once a material has been extracted from the biosphere, it remains in circulation indefinitely.

Industrial ecology is an academic field with its roots in similar concepts to the circular economy. It grew out of the idea that industrial activity should more closely resemble that of a biological ecosystem [36], in which the waste products of one industrial process can be used, or be engineered to be used, as the inputs to another industrial process [37]. The science of industrial ecology and the related quantitative tools, including materials flow analysis (MFA) and life cycle assessment (LCA), have been proposed as a way to systematically investigate the potential, the application and, importantly, the limitations of the circular economy [38].

An important part of industrial ecology is the idea of *industrial symbiosis*. Based upon the idea of symbiosis in biology, where two organisms gain mutual benefit from long standing cooperation, industrial symbiosis refers to the exchange of materials, energy, water, or by-products by traditionally unrelated industries, for mutual benefit [39].

The concept of industrial symbiosis was inspired by and is exemplified in the eco-industrial park at Kalundborg in Denmark. Here the co-location of an oil refinery, a power station, an acid plant, a gypsum board plant and a pharmaceutical plant led to the exchange of waste materials (e.g. flue gas scrubber sludge from the power plant to the gypsum board factory, extracted sulphur from the oil refinery to the acid plant), exchange of waste heat (as steam, from the power plant to the oil refinery and the pharmaceutical plant) and the pooling of natural resources (in the sequential use of cooling water by the oil refinery and the power plant) [39]. Interestingly, the environmental benefits of this cooperation were only recognised decades after the cooperation had been established [39].

The valorisation of bauxite residue has the potential to be considered a part of a subtype of industrial symbiosis related to by-product exchange [40].

2.3.4 *Criticisms of the zero-waste approach*

While closed loop systems are a good idea in theory, in practice there are issues which need to be confronted. There is a balance between the environmental burdens avoided from material displacement, and the additional environmental burdens which are accrued in order to facilitate their reuse. Proponents of the circular economy commonly downplay or overlook such issues as the energy requirements and inherent material losses associated with closed loops [41].

As pointed out by Boulding [32], the maintenance of materials within a closed system must be paid for by inputs of energy, and, thanks to the second law of thermodynamics, this requires a continuing input of energy into the system. In order for a circular economy to be truly sustainable, the energy needed to power these cycles must come from renewable sources. Until this is the case, the circular economy could possibly be an exercise in burden shifting, from material extraction to energy generation.

Recycling requires less energy than the virgin production of most commonly recycled materials [18], thus even in the absence of an entirely renewable energy system, increased recycling rates and an increasing circularity to material flows within the economy would represent a move in the right direction. However, when extending circular economy ideals to uncommonly recycled materials, bauxite residue included, this rule may not hold. That is, the energy required to obtain a given material via valorisation or recycling may be greater than the energy required for the equivalent primary production.

For some, this is not seen as problematic, for example proponents of the Cradle to Cradle (C2C) concept, where material circularity is prized over energy efficiency [42]. Here the theory goes that in a world where all energy requirements are derived from current solar income (i.e. renewable energy sources), the effectiveness with which materials can be recycled is more important than the efficiency with which this recycling takes place. However, this theory breaks down in a world where the entire global energy system is not 100% renewable. Indeed Bjørn and Hauschild [43] note that under current conditions, products certified according to the C2C product standards can exhibit lower environmental performance than equivalent conventional products in LCA studies.

Alongside material circularity, a move to 100% renewable energy is a core tenet of the broader circular economy ideal [35], and therefore, in the long term, any increase in energy use through the

introduction of unconventional recycling or valorisation systems would not necessarily result in increased environmental impacts. However, one could argue that the benefits associated with an increase in the proportion of renewable energy are separate from the benefits of material circularity, and are therefore equally as valid within a linear economy as they are within a circular one.

In addition to the potential for increased energy use, the potential for loss of quality in closed loop recycling systems can also represent a significant issue in some cases. Cullen [41] points to the example of recycled concrete. Currently, not only does crushing waste concrete to aggregate require energy, but when used to create new concrete, more virgin cement is required to bind these aggregates than would be the case for traditional aggregate. The energy and material requirements incurred by starting with a lower quality material outweigh the perceived benefits of resource conservation via recycling.

The perpetual cycling of materials within a zero-waste society may also lead to the unwanted cycling of persistent toxicants within products due to contamination, or the build-up of stocks of toxic materials, for example mercury, from older products which have no outlet in the current economy [44]. The unwanted cycling of contaminants is of potential significance with regard to the naturally occurring radionuclides present in low levels in bauxite residue.

Perhaps the most useful definition of 'zero-waste' is that proposed by Defra in the UK. Zero-waste is defined as '*a simple way of encapsulating the aim to go as far as possible in reducing the environmental impact of waste. It is a visionary goal which seeks to prevent waste occurring, conserves resources and recovers all value from materials*' [45 p. 336]. This offers a compromise between the 'visionary' theoretical benefits of perpetual material cycling and the practical realities associated with achieving this aim. Aiming for zero-waste without losing sight of the fact that the real goal is to reduce environmental impact is an important motivation for this thesis.

2.3.5 *Dimensions of environmental impact*

The task of demonstrating the potential environmental benefits of zero-waste systems is further complicated by the multifaceted nature of *environmental impact* itself. Human activities have an impact on the environment in many different ways and by many different

causal pathways. There is no single indicator of environmental impact.

In addition, people's perceptions about what is important in terms of the environment are not static through time. Concerns about acid rain, the hole in the ozone layer and now the climate crisis have led to the emission of acid gases, CFCs and greenhouse gases gaining successive prominence in the minds of the public and policy makers. Air quality is now emerging as a growing concern, with the WHO reporting that poor outdoor air quality is responsible for three million deaths annually [46].

Commonly however environmental impacts can be attributed to the same underlying causes, and are therefore correlated, raising hopes that fewer environmental indicators may be required to capture the effect of multiple impacts. For example, Huijbregts et al. [47] found that for energy generation, material production and transport processes, cumulative fossil energy demand correlated well with other impacts including global warming, acidification, eutrophication, photochemical ozone formation and resource depletion. This is as a result of the large contribution of fossil fuels to each of these impacts.

However, for processes where non-fossil emissions are important, such as agricultural and waste treatment processes, and for categories of impact with a weaker link to fossil fuel use, such as toxicity and land use, the correlation is weaker [47]. Technological developments, such as end-of-pipe treatments for off-gases from energy generation were also noted to weaken the correlation of fossil fuel use and impacts such as acidification. Widespread uptake of carbon capture and storage would also weaken this correlation with climate change impact.

In order to capture the overall impact of a given process, it is therefore necessary to measure this impact on multiple environmental dimensions. The impact measures which are relevant will depend in part on the particulars of the product system being studied. For bauxite residue valorisation, in addition to the most commonly assessed environmental impacts, exposure to ionising radiation from natural radionuclides is a potentially important impact measure.

2.4 Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM)

2.4.1 *Natural radiation*

Natural sources of radiation are the most significant contributor to the worldwide annual per capita ionising radiation dose received by humans, accounting for 80% of the total dose [48]. Primordial isotopes, those with a half-life comparable to the age of the earth, and their decay chains account for 80% of this natural radiation [48].

Humans and biota have evolved in the presence of background natural radiation for millions of years, however human activities have the potential to concentrate and redistribute natural radionuclides to such an extent that the levels of exposure can have adverse effects health effects [49,50]. At this point, natural radionuclides become a radioprotection issue.

Where human activity leads to a material presenting an increased risk of radiation exposure from natural radionuclides, these materials are designated as Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM). This enhanced exposure may result from humans placing themselves in greater proximity to these materials, either as workers (e.g. miners) or more generally, for example, by using natural materials rich in such radionuclides as residential building materials. Alternatively, some human actions lead to the concentration of natural radionuclides, for example coal combustion leading to a concentration of radionuclides in ash. Some authors, particularly in the oil and gas industry, separately classify these types of materials as Technologically Enhanced NORMs (TENORM) [51,52]. These kinds of activities can also lead to the release of natural radionuclides to the environment.

2.4.2 *Natural radiation and bauxite residue*

The three most important natural radioisotopes from a radioprotection perspective are ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K [53]. All three of these radionuclides are present in bauxite, and as a consequence of the Bayer process are concentrated in bauxite residue. Levels of ^{238}U and ^{232}Th can be 2-3 times higher in the bauxite residue leaving the Bayer process than in the original bauxite [54].

Currently this only presents a potential issue to workers at Bayer plants, and even then only in extreme cases. The annual occupational dose limit in the EU (set in the Basic Safety Standards Directive [55]) of 20 mSv/a is sufficiently high that NORM exposure to Bayer plant workers is not of regulatory concern.

One potential avenue of research within the REDMUD project however is the use of bauxite residue in high proportions in building materials. The regulatory dose limit for members of the public is much lower (1 mSv/a), and the time people spend in proximity to residential building materials is much higher than the time spent by workers in proximity to bauxite residue at Bayer plants. Management of bauxite residue also has the potential to cause releases of natural radionuclides to the environment.

As a result, changes to the way in which bauxite residue is managed may lead to changes in the ionising radiation dose received by the general public and by ecosystems. These changes need to be understood and taken into account in the environmental assessment of bauxite residue valorisation options.

3 Methods

3.1 Research strategy/research design

The approach to each of the research questions addressed in this thesis is underpinned by Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). RQ3 and RQ4 (assessment of single and multi-stage valorisation pathways) are primarily answered using LCA. The key concepts of LCA most relevant to this thesis are described in section 3.2.

The integration of NORM exposure into LCA (RQ1) requires the overall LCA framework to be extended through the development of a new Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) characterisation method. This involves the application of methods borrowed from the fields of radiological modelling and toxicology. These are described in section 3.3.

RQ2 concerning LCA modelling using lab scale data requires an understanding of foreground modelling in LCA and the various approaches used to translate the description of a process into a useful LCA model. These are described in section 3.4.

Table 2: Methods used to address each research questions

#	Research Question	LCA	LCIA development	LCA foreground modelling
1.	Integration of NORM exposure into LCA	✓	✓	
2.	LCA modelling approaches	✓		✓
3.	Assessment of single stage valorisation pathways	✓		
4.	Assessment of multi-stage valorisation pathways	✓		

3.2 Life Cycle Assessment

3.2.1 Overview

The impact we as humans have on the environment is mediated by the complex network of products and processes we have built up around ourselves in order to function in our daily lives. This *technosphere* interacts with the environment (the *biosphere*), via the exchange of substances and energy, either from the biosphere to the technosphere as resources, or from the technosphere to the biosphere, as emissions and waste.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a quantitative methodology which can be used to understand the potential environmental impacts which result from the whole life cycle of a given product or service, through the quantification and characterisation of these exchanges between the technosphere and biosphere. This encompasses extraction of raw materials from the environment, the production, distribution and use of a given product, and its final disposal at the end of its useful life (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Resource and emission flows (exchanges) between the technosphere and the biosphere over the life cycle of a product.

LCA is a relatively mature and internationally recognised methodology; the principles and requirements of LCA are standardised by the International Organisation for Standardisation [22,56], and there is a peer reviewed journal dedicated to it (the International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment [57]).

A Life Cycle Assessment study consists of four main phases: goal and scope definition; inventory analysis; impact assessment; and

interpretation. These phases are iterative, and information gained from one phase may influence the approach taken in another, for example altering the system boundary (see section 3.2.2) as a result of interesting environmental aspects revealed at the impact assessment stage (3.2.4). The most important aspects of these stages in relation to this thesis are briefly described below.

3.2.2 Goal and Scope definition

At the outset of an LCA study, certain methodological choices have to be made in order to constrain and define the study. These choices will depend on the goal of the study. LCA can be used for many purposes, but the most common goals of an LCA include: identifying hotspots of environmental impact and opportunities to improve the environmental performance of a product; providing decision support in choosing between two or more alternatives on the basis of environmental performance; and, as the basis for making marketing claims including environmental labelling (ecolabels) [22].

The methodological decisions made in order to define the LCA are referred to as the scope of the LCA. The scope of the LCA includes the definition of the *functional unit*, the setting of *system boundaries*, the choice of *system model* and the choice of *impact assessment methods*.

The functional unit in LCA is a quantified and well defined measure of the function of a product (or service). The life cycle impacts of a given product system which produces this product are calculated relative to the production one functional unit. This allows for fair comparisons to be made between divergent product systems producing functionally equivalent products. Functional units can be relatively simple, or more complex depending on the requirements of the LCA. For example in Paper V the functional unit is defined as:

The provision of 1 m² of paving blocks, of thickness 50 mm, with a design life of 20 years

This allows the fair comparison of multiple options for the composition and production of paving blocks, in line with the goal of the study. In the case study in paper II however, a more complex functional unit is required. In this study we wished to compare different methods of managing bauxite residue – via landfill or recycling into building materials. Here we chose to use an ‘equal basket of benefits’ approach [58,59] resulting in a composite functional unit, where each scenario provided the treatment of 1 kg

of bauxite residue, and the provision of 2.47 kg of bricks and 22.4 kg of cement.

The *system boundary* in LCA determines which processes in the life cycle are taken into account in the study and which are excluded. In comparative studies for example, processes in the life cycle which are identical across all scenarios can be excluded from the system boundary, as they will have no influence on the final comparison [17]. This means that effort is not wasted on data collection and modelling for unnecessary elements of the life cycle.

A *system model* in LCA is a set of modelling choices and assumptions which determine how the linking of processes and allocation of impacts should occur within an LCA model [60]. LCA system models are typically categorised according to two main modelling approaches: *attributorial* and *consequential*.

There is no agreed definition of the terms *attributorial* and *consequential* modelling in LCA, and multiple slightly different descriptions are in common usage [61]. Broadly speaking, the attributorial approach provides a descriptive assessment of the potential environmental impact associated with the life cycle of a given product. The consequential approach in contrast provides an assessment of the magnitude of potential environmental impacts associated with a change in demand for a given product, including the consequences of this change on other product systems [62]. A detailed discussion of the attributes and relative merits of attributorial and consequential approaches to LCA is beyond the scope of this thesis (for this, readers are referred to references [61–69]), and the debate as to when to use each of these approaches is ongoing in the LCA literature [65,67,68,70].

The position of Suh and Yang [70] – that the distinction between the attributorial and consequential approaches to LCA is a false dichotomy, and that each are in fact points on a spectrum of approaches – is closest to my personal stance on this issue. They invoke the oft-used quote in this regard, that *'All models are wrong, but some are useful'* [71]. The studies included in this thesis have the overarching aim to identify the advantages and disadvantages associated with different, emerging technologies. A descriptive analysis of the potential environmental impacts associated with these technologies is the most useful approach at this stage, and therefore an attributorial approach and an attributorial background database [60] were used in the LCAs in this thesis.

The choice of impact assessment methods in LCA is of particular relevance to this thesis. While some LCA studies may choose to focus

on a particular category of environmental impact, for example carbon footprint studies will focus only on global warming impact [72], studies of this type are vulnerable to *burden shifting* (see section 2.1). From the opposite perspective however, it is important that the methods used to characterise and assess the environmental impacts are rigorously developed, compatible with the data used in a model and appropriate for use in a given analysis. There are a wide range of impact characterisation methods available for use in LCA (the LCA software Brightway2 contains 718 individual built in methods [73]⁶). In an attempt to rationalise this situation, the European Commission have published (as part of the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD)) an assessment of impact assessment methods [74]. In addition to recommending 12 impact assessment models, this document provides guidelines as to what constitutes a ‘good’ impact assessment method. The 12 ILCD recommended impact categories were used as the basis of the analysis in Paper V, while the impact assessment method developed in Papers I and II was developed with the ILCD criteria in mind.

3.2.3 Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) analysis

The preparation of the Life Cycle Inventory is the quantitative core of LCA. It consists of two steps: the construction of the *foreground model*, and the compilation of the overall Life Cycle Inventory (LCI).

The *foreground model* is a collection of linked *unit processes* – discreet transformative actions within the life cycle of a product – which describe the product system being assessed. There are many approaches to generating a foreground model (discussed in section 3.4), and the extent of the foreground model will vary depending on the goal of the study.

For each unit process in the foreground model, each of the inputs from the technosphere (materials and energy), outputs to the technosphere (products, by-products and wastes), resources extracted from the biosphere, and emissions to the biosphere are listed and quantified. Inputs to a unit process may be an output of another unit process within the foreground model, or may come from the *background system*. The background system is usually a large interconnected database of life cycle inventory data, such as the ecoinvent database [60].

⁶ These 718 methods represent methodological variants of around 30 environmental impact measures.

Once the foreground model has been created and linked to the background system, LCA software is used to compile the LCI. The LCI is the aggregated sum of each of the exchanges between the biosphere and the technosphere resulting from each of the unit processes in the foreground and background systems required to produce the functional unit. In its simplest form this is a quantified list of resources extracted from and emissions released to the environment. The emission and resource exchanges in the compiled LCI can then be characterised according to their impact on the environment in the next stage of the LCA.

3.2.4 Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The LCI describes the exchanges between the technosphere and biosphere that occur as a result of the life cycle of a given product, but it does not tell us anything about the potential for those exchanges to cause an environmental impact. In order to understand the environmental impact these exchanges cause, each exchange must be *characterised* according to the impact they have in a given category.

For example, releases of greenhouse gases (e.g. carbon dioxide, methane, HFCs) will have an impact on climate change. An *impact assessment model* is used to characterise the impact that the release of one kg of each of these gases will have on climate change, in this case based on the amount of radiative forcing they cause in the atmosphere, relative to carbon dioxide. This allows each greenhouse gas to be allocated a *characterisation factor* for climate change impact, with the unit kgCO₂-eq/kg. Each kg of greenhouse gas recorded in the LCI can be multiplied by its characterisation factor, to generate a *characterised inventory*. This characterised inventory can be summed to give the total climate change impact resulting from the life cycle of the product being assessed.

RQ1, addressed by Papers I and II, concerns the development of an impact assessment model for exposure to NORM.

3.3 Life Cycle Impact Assessment models

A Life Cycle Impact Assessment model is a mathematical representation of a cause-effect chain, which begins with the release of a substance into the environment and ends with a quantifiable impact [75]. The calculations required to model this cause-effect

chain are commonly based on sophisticated natural science based models. These models are domain specific, depending on the impact considered, and a broad range of models are used to generate LCIA characterisation factors [76]. For example, the most commonly used climate change impact characterisation factors are based on physical models of the behaviour of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere and the degree of radiative forcing they exert [77].

While the radiative forcing model itself may be complex, in the case of climate change, the cause-effect chain is relatively simple. A gas is released to the atmosphere, and while it remains there it has a global radiative forcing effect. As a result, climate change impact is considered a robust LCIA method, and is commonly emphasised in LCA studies [74]. In contrast, the cause-effect chain for other impacts, especially those regarding toxicity impacts to humans and biota, are much more complex. The impact assessment models developed in Papers I and II involve such a complex cause-effect chain.

3.3.1 Source pathway receptor framework

A commonly used method to understand toxicity impacts of environmental releases is the ‘source – pathway – receptor’ framework [78]. In order for the release of a substance to the environment to cause an impact, all three of these elements must be in place. That is, the fact that a source of pollution exists is *necessary* but not *sufficient* for it to cause an impact. In order for an impact to occur a pathway between this source and a vulnerable receptor (commonly humans, a particular habitat or ecosystem, etc.) must also exist. This framework is commonly applied in pragmatic approaches to environmental protection and environmental risk assessment, for example in waste management [79] and oil and gas sectors [80].

In the context of LCIA modelling, the inventoried releases of substances (recorded in the LCI) constitute the *source* term of this framework. The first stage in the *pathway* can be modelled using environmental fate modelling. These commonly take the form of multi-media environmental partitioning models, which calculate the likely distribution of a given chemical within different *compartments* within the environment (e.g. air, freshwater, seawater, soil), based on their physical properties [81]. This results in an indication of the likely potential exposure level within each of these compartments.

The second part of the *pathway* is calculated via *exposure modelling* [82]. This is used to determine, given a certain level of a substance within a compartment, how much will be transferred to the receptor population in a way in which it will cause an impact. This includes inhalation of contaminated air and ingestion of contaminated water, soil or foodstuffs [82].

This final stage is to calculate the magnitude of the toxicity effect on the receptor based on the estimated potential exposure. For chemical toxicity effects, dose response values (ED₁₀/ED₅₀) or concentration response values (EC₁₀/EC₅₀) are recommended to estimate the impact [83,84]. These are the dose level (typically used in mammalian studies) or concentration levels in water (typically used for aquatic organisms) at which a toxicity effect is observed in 10% or 50% of the population respectively.

3.3.2 Radiological dose and impact measures

For radiological effects, such as those resulting from NORM exposure, the ED₁₀/ED₅₀ concept is still useful, however the dose received by a receptor is more complex than for chemical exposure. In addition to internal dose from inhalation and ingestion, an ionising radiation dose can be received externally from the environment.

For radioactive substances, releases to the environment are inventoried in units of activity - the becquerel (Bq) - rather than units of mass (kg). A Becquerel is equal to one disintegration of a radioactive nucleus per second [85]. The *absorbed radiation dose* received by a receptor is measured in Grays (Gy)[85], which are a measure of energy absorbed per unit mass [86]. One Gray is equal to one Joule of energy absorbed by one kg of matter. However, different body tissues are sensitive to ionising radiation to varying degrees. In order to more accurately represent the potential damage caused by radiation, the radiation absorbed is weighted by the sensitivity of each of the tissues in the receptor in order to calculate the *effective radiation dose* [86]. This effective dose is measured in units of Sievert (Sv).

For the radiological impact models used in Papers I and II, the key addition to the exposure modelling outlined above is the use of Dose Conversion Coefficients (DCCs) for internal and external radiation exposure. These coefficients are calculated using a set of average body related and physiological parameters referred to as the *Reference Man* [87]. DCCs can be used to convert a level of activity

(measured in Bq) in a given exposure situation (e.g. inhalation) for a given radionuclide into an effective dose (measured in Sv). These coefficients provide the link between the exposure and effect models for radiological impact.

3.3.3 *Midpoint and Endpoint indicators*

One further important distinction within LCIA modelling is that between *midpoint* and *endpoint* indicators. These refer to the point along the cause-effect chain at which the impact is measured. Midpoint indicators are defined at a point in the cause-effect chain at which the effect of the full variety of substances can be ascribed to single common mechanism, and measured in a common unit [75]. For example, the radiative forcing mechanism (relative to that of CO₂), measured in units of kg CO₂-eq, is the midpoint indicator for climate change impact. For global impacts such as climate change, midpoint indicators provide a good indication of impact [75].

For the human health radiological impact model presented in Papers I and II, the midpoint indicator is measured in man.Sv, representing the collective radiation dose received by the population from the various radionuclides considered. However, it is possible to go one step further down the cause-effect chain to calculate the potential damage to human health which may result from this collective dose. This is an endpoint measure. In this case it is measured in Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) [88] – a measure of increased morbidity and mortality which results from exposure to a given stressor, in this case radiation dose.

One benefit of endpoint measures is that they can be compared across different impact mechanisms, for example, in addition to radiation impact, the endpoint impact of both chemical toxicity and airborne particulates on human health can also be measured in DALY. The relative magnitude of these sources of impact can therefore be compared at the interpretation phase of the LCA study. However, the further along the cause-effect chain an impact is measured, the greater the level of uncertainty there is associated with it. There is therefore a trade-off between this level of analysis and the explanatory power which can be ascribed to endpoint measures, which must be considered in the interpretation.

3.4 Life cycle foreground modelling

3.4.1 *Foreground vs Background system*

The product systems studied using LCA consist of a vast web of interconnected processes. In order to make data collection and interpretation of the results manageable, LCA models are divided into the *foreground* and *background* systems [17]. Generally speaking, primary data is collected in order to describe the foreground system, while secondary data from published sources is used to populate the background system [63].

There is no formal definition of the foreground system in LCA; it is not specified in the ISO standards concerning LCA [22,56]. The distinction between the foreground system and the background system can therefore be determined by the goal and scope of the study. There are two commonly held perspectives on the distinction between the foreground and background systems, known as the *specificity perspective*, and the *management perspective* [63].

Under the specificity perspective, the foreground model is determined by the processes which are specific to the system being studied. Processes which could be replaced by market average data without changing the specifics of the product (for example electricity generation processes) are considered part of the background system. This perspective is useful for LCAs for marketing claims and ecolabels [63].

Under the management perspective, the focus is shifted towards decision making potential. The foreground system is made up of processes where the selection or mode of operation may be influenced by the results of the study. Those processes over which the author, or audience, of the study have no control are placed in the background system. This perspective is particularly useful for change-orientated and prospective LCAs [63].

3.4.2 *Modelling approaches*

Models of the foreground system (foreground models) are commonly represented as process flow diagrams. Indeed drawing a process flow diagram is recommended in the ISO 14044 standard [56], as well as the Handbook on Life Cycle Assessment [89] and the guide to the PAS 2050 product carbon footprinting standard [90].

In most LCA software packages (e.g. SimaPro [91], OpenLCA [92], Brightway2 [73]) these flow diagrams must be manually transcribed into a series of tables, listing input and output flows for

each process. In Paper III, an alternative approach is presented. This paper is actually a piece of peer-reviewed LCA software in which process flow diagrams can be created via the user interface. The possibility of simplifying LCA foreground modelling for non LCA experts is further explored in Paper IV, where a method to identify the key characteristics of hand-drawn LCA process flow diagrams using computer vision is proposed. A separate piece of software capable of generating a fully functioning LCA foreground model from a photograph of a hand-drawn diagram accompanies this paper.

3.4.3 *Parameterisation*

Paper III also introduces the idea of *parameterisation* of the foreground model. In the tabular compilation of an LCA model described above, each flow has to be given an amount. These values are commonly *hardcoded* – entered as a literal value – within the table which defines the unit process. For situations where the model only represents one well-defined and unchanging system, this is perfectly adequate.

The LCA conducted in Paper V is an example of a situation where multiple variants of a base model need to be analysed as part of the study to reflect different scenarios. Using the hardcoding approach described above would require that a new, duplicate copy of the model be created for each scenario, and the flow values in each new version of the model changed individually. To avoid this, flow values can instead be defined by *parameters*.

In this case, flows in a unit process are assigned a named parameter rather than a literal value. The value of this parameter is defined externally to the unit process in a convenient location, for example as part of a *parameter set* which describes a scenario. By modelling with parameters, different versions of the base model representing different scenarios can be created and analysed simply by providing a new parameter set to the model. Most LCA software has the option to use parameters, but it is not the default. The software presented in Paper III and utilised in Papers V and VI generates *fully-parameterised* models, in which every flow is designated by a parameter.

Parameterisation has the additional benefit that parameters can be defined by formulas. This means that flows for which there is a causal link – for example input of a fuel, and emissions of carbon dioxide – can be mathematically linked within the model. In this case

changing the fuel input parameter would automatically calculate the correct value for the emissions parameter.

3.4.4 *Anticipatory/Prospective LCA*

The new technologies assessed in this thesis for the valorisation of bauxite residue are currently in development at lab scale, and therefore by definition, no industrial scale data is available. This is a common problem in the environmental assessment of emerging technologies.

In response, a form of LCA known as *anticipatory* or *prospective* LCA has emerged [93]. The ethos of anticipatory LCA is closely aligned with the management perspective outlined in section 3.4.1. In anticipatory studies, the focus of the modelling is on the potential environmental impacts which may result from possible changes to the system resulting from research and development (R&D) decisions. In addition however, there is a greater focus on using various modelling techniques to overcome the lack of accurate datasets to describe these processes at industrial scale.

An important part of this approach is the use of mathematical models of a hypothetical industrial process - based on the data obtained from lab scale experiments and combined with reasonable and justifiable assumptions – instead of using the primary data generated at lab scale directly. Even in the absence of specific data, such models can provide upper and/or lower bounds for parameters based on physical, chemical or thermodynamic constraints. This approach has been applied in a broad range of use cases, including biofuels [94–96], gasification [97] and bio-refinery systems [98].

Another important approach is to identify the key design variables within a system, and conduct multiple parallel analyses (different scenarios) to investigate the importance of these variables [93]. This approach can be used to identify the potential areas of a product or product system where either the most impact is likely to be present, or where the most potential for reduction may lie. An anticipatory LCA approach is used in Paper V to understand where the greatest potential to reduce the environmental impact of the process to create inorganic polymers from bauxite residue lies, and in doing so inform the direction of future research.

4 Results and Analysis

In this section, the results obtained in the appended papers are presented and interpreted in relation to each of the research questions outlined in section 1.2 in turn.

4.1 Integration of NORM exposure into LCA

Can, and should, the enhanced exposure to Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM) resulting from industrial processes, including the valorisation of bauxite residue, be integrated into the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework?

In a world where 718 LCIA methods can be included as standard in an LCA software package [73] but only 12 are recommended for use by the EU JRC [74], the proposed development of a new LCIA method needs to be critically considered. In Paper I we took such a critical view, and determined that it was indeed both desirable and feasible to develop such a method for the enhanced exposure of humans and ecosystems to ionising radiation from NORM nuclides.

Firstly we determined that the two currently available ionising radiation LCIA methods [86,99] were insufficient to account for the impact of NORM on both humans and ecosystems. Both of these methods were developed to assess the impact of operational releases of radionuclides from the nuclear fuel cycle. These releases are mainly of artificial nuclides generated during the fission reactions. None of the three major NORM nuclide decay chains (^{238}U , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K) were considered in the ecosystem impact category [99], while only airborne emissions of ^{238}U were considered for human health impact [86]. We further determined that a major exposure route of humans to NORM nuclides is via products incorporated into the built environment. This exposure route is not included in the current ionising radiation impact category, as the use of materials generated in the nuclear fuel cycle in building materials is highly unlikely to ever be considered.

Having determined that the ionising radiation impacts associated with NORM were not already considered in LCA, we subsequently used the framework of Cucurachi et al. [76] to assess whether these impacts should be considered for inclusion in the LCA framework.

The Cucurachi framework sets out six requisite criteria to determine whether an impact model should be developed for LCA.

The full wording of the requirements is given in Table 2 of Paper I, however, these can be summarised as follows:

1. Evidence of a mechanistic link between exposure and impact exists
2. There is a standardised quantification method for the proposed impact
3. The importance of the impact has been recognised by an international agency
4. Trends suggest the impact is likely to grow
5. The impact occurs at multiple life cycle stages
6. Sufficient information exists to study the impact in relation to a specific area of protection

We determined that each of these criteria was satisfied by our proposed NORM exposure impact category (Paper I, Table 2).

Consequently, the next stage was to identify the most important potential exposure pathways between sources of NORM, and possible receptors. Figure 3 summarises these exposure pathways.

Figure 3. Potential exposure pathways to NORM radionuclides as a result of NORM processing (Source: Paper I, figure 2).

Releases of NORM to air and water are subsequently dispersed and transported through the environment, and can end up impacting upon human and non-human receptors. This dispersal and transport takes place via various mechanisms including deposition, translocation, ingestion and bioaccumulation, and is represented in the bottom half of Figure 3.

In addition to pathways resulting from releases of NORM nuclides to the environment, the top half of Figure 3 shows the potential for exposure to ionising radiation from materials containing NORM nuclides. This can occur while processing materials, for example placing them in landfill, or, more significantly, via materials incorporated into the built environment.

In addition to external exposure to gamma radiation, which occurs in all three major decay chains, the ^{238}U decay chain includes gaseous ^{222}Rn . This radioactive gas can accumulate inside dwellings built with NORM containing materials, and presents an additional exposure route with the potential to impact upon human health.

In order to create an impact assessment model for NORM exposure, each of these potential pathways of exposure needed to be modelled mathematically. We devised a framework, in which each pathway was broken down into discrete ‘fate’, ‘exposure’ and ‘damage’ models, which would allow a composite model to be developed, ideally using existing models as the building blocks (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Proposed framework for NORM in LCA (Source: Paper I, figure 3)

We subsequently reviewed the LCA and radiological literature to identify potential candidate models and approaches which could be incorporated into this framework. Table 3 shows the existing models we identified as most suitable for inclusion, with the level of revision required in order to facilitate their inclusion.

Table 3. Models identified as most suitable for inclusion in the NORM/LCA framework. Details of the references in the table can be found in Paper I. (Source: Paper I, table 8)

LCA step	Release to the environment		Occupational exposure				Building materials				
	Human impact	Biota impact	Human impact				Human impact				
			Storage	Handling	Gamma dose	Radon dose					
Inventory analysis	Mass balance		*	Measurements	*	Impact considered negligible	Measurements		*		
Fate analysis	USEtox (Rosenbaum et al. 2008)		***	Markkanen(1995)	**		Considered to be immobile	x	UNSCEAR(2000)	**	
Exposure analysis	UNSCEAR (2000)	**	ERICA (Brown et al. 2008)	***	UNSCEAR (2000)		**	Meijer et al. (2005)	**	UNSCEAR (2000)	**
								UNSCEAR (2000) for effective dose	**		
Damage analysis	Disability adjusted life years (DALY) (Frischknecht and Braunschweig 2000)	*	Screening level ecological risk assessment(Brown et al. 2008)	*	Disability adjusted life years (DALY) (Frischknecht and Braunschweig 2000)	*	Disability adjusted life years (DALY) (Frischknecht and Braunschweig 2000)		*		

* Model requires little or no revision **Model requires minimal revision ***Model requires extensive additions/revisions X Not relevant

In terms of the original research question, Paper I confirms that the impact of NORM exposure *should* be included in LCA. In proposing the framework for the impact assessment method it goes some way to answering whether this method *can* be devised.

Paper II describes the implementation of the framework set out in Paper I, and in doing so confirms that the impact assessment model can indeed be successfully created and used. This implementation takes the form of an Excel file which is available as part of the electronic supplementary materials for Paper II.

The implementation resulted in four different impact methods, one for the impact to human health, and three further methods to assess the impact on terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems. Each of these methods has a midpoint indicator and an endpoint indicator. For human health, the midpoint indicator was collective radiation dose (measured in man.Sv) and the endpoint indicator was the damage caused by this dose, measured in disability adjusted life years (DALY). For ecosystems, we used the concept of Potentially

Affected Fraction of species (ΔPAF) [100] for the midpoint indicator. This concept unites the lethal and non-lethal effects to organism groups within an ecosystem based on the level of chronic exposure, providing a single aggregated measure for each ecosystem. The related concept of Potentially Disappeared Fraction (ΔPDF) was used as the endpoint indicator for ecosystems.

As the three ecosystem impact categories are measured in the same unit, they could in theory be combined into a single ‘ecosystems’ category. We did not take this approach, for two reasons. Firstly, by presenting the characterisation factors in a disaggregated manner, it allows users of the method to combine them if they wish. Secondly, in the type of compartmental fate modelling used, the marine environment tends to act as a sink for persistent pollutants, including radionuclides. The marine characterisation factors are therefore comparatively large, and would potentially dominate the results of such a combined method.

In order to test and validate the impact assessment model, we performed a case study investigating three different ways of treating bauxite residue: disposal in landfill, valorisation in bricks and valorisation in cement. In order to ensure this assessment represented a fair comparison, an ‘equal basket of benefits’ approach was used. In this approach a composite functional unit is used. In each of the three scenarios, this ‘basket of benefits’ consists of the treatment of 1kg of bauxite residue, and the provision of 2.47 kg of bricks and 22.4 kg of cement (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Scenario process diagram for the case study in Paper II (Source: Paper II, figure 3)

The results for human health impact show that the overall impact from NORM exposure is similar across the three scenarios (Figure 6). The scenario in which bauxite residue is sent to landfill has the lowest overall impact, while the reuse scenario for bauxite residue in cement has the highest impact. In both reuse scenarios, there is an additional impact which results from exposure to the elevated level of radionuclides in the bauxite residue during their use in dwellings. The slight increase in impact for the cement scenario results from the higher porosity of concrete leading to greater radon exhalation into the living space.

Figure 6. Processes contributing to NORM exposure in humans. TSC: Traditional Supply Chain. Solid bar: gamma doses, hatched bar: radon dose. (Source: Paper II, figure 4)

In terms of exposure routes, the impact to human health from NORM contained within building materials is many orders of magnitude greater than the impact to humans resulting from NORM nuclides released to, and subsequently dispersed within, the environment. In all three scenarios, the impact from the traditional supply chain materials (bricks and cement) is the largest contribution to human health impact. This is due to the presence (albeit at lower levels) of NORM radionuclides in these materials, and the higher amounts required in the functional unit. Taken together, these two results confirm that it is important for NORM exposure to be considered in LCA using our newly devised impact assessment method. This impact exposure route is not only relevant for waste derived materials, but also for commonly used materials, and has not been accounted for in past studies.

This conclusion is further backed up when considering the endpoint results for NORM exposure. As these results were calculated in units of DALY, it was possible to compare the relative impact of NORM exposure and other impact measures which cause damage to human health (Figure 7). NORM exposure is the most significant impact category in the life cycle impact of all three scenarios.

From an ecosystems perspective, the landfill scenario caused the greatest NORM exposure impact for all three ecosystems, primarily due to long term emissions from landfill. Long term in this context means emissions that will occur between 100 and 60,000 years into the future. There is a great deal of uncertainty surrounding the long term behaviour of material in landfill. The ecosystem results were highly sensitive to the assumption that, in the very long term, 100% of the radionuclides contained within bauxite residue would be released to groundwater.

A particular feature of radionuclide emissions to the environment is that as each radionuclide decays, it transforms into a different element. This element will have different properties to its parent nuclide, and as a result will disperse within the environment in a different manner. This is a similar problem to that seen for organic pollutants, where degradation products, which may themselves also be toxic, will exhibit different environmental behaviour to the original compound. USEtox [101], the de-facto standard for toxicity modelling in LCA, ignores the behaviour of degradation products. We investigated the sensitivity of the case study results to the different distribution effects of daughter nuclides. While the effect was small for human health impacts, the ecosystem

results proved more sensitive to the effects of daughter nuclide redistribution. As a result we conclude that the human health NORM exposure impact method is a useful addition to the LCA framework, while the ecosystem methods are of more limited applicability.

Figure 7. Total potential contribution to human health from different impact categories for Scenario 2 (use of BR in bricks). Bold type indicates new NORM endpoint measures, * indicates endpoint methods considered interim by ILCD. (Source: Paper II, figure 8)

Paper V, in which we investigate hotspots of environmental impact in the production of inorganic polymer paving blocks from bauxite residue, constitutes the first ‘real-world’ use of the human health NORM exposure method. In this paper we also extend the NORM exposure method to include use phase exposure from pavement products (in addition to residential applications from Paper II). This further allows us to conclude that the inclusion of NORM exposure in the LCA framework is a useful and worthwhile enterprise, both for valorisation systems, and for industrial processes more generally.

4.2 LCA modelling approaches

What is the most suitable approach to modelling the industrial scale life cycle impacts of bauxite residue valorisation using lab scale data?

The nature of the data generated by the REDMUD project researchers is such that *full LCA* modelling approaches are not appropriate for understanding the environmental impact of the technologies being developed. *Full LCA* requires a well-defined and specified product system, from which extensive primary data, ideally from multiple tiers of the supply chain can be collected [63]. The early stage, lab-scale experiments carried out by the REDMUD researchers are a long way from being able to provide this level of data, but this does not mean that LCA approaches cannot be used to provide useful information about the potential environmental implications of these technologies.

Multiple approaches have been suggested for streamlining LCA, primarily in situations where time and/or resources are limited; however these tend to focus on limiting the amount of primary data that needs to be collected at the LCI stage [102]. For situations where primary data do not yet exist, such as in the design or research and development processes, prospective or anticipatory LCA approaches [93] are more appropriate. This is the most suitable approach for the REDMUD project.

The LCA approach taken in this thesis had to be tailored in order to fit the information which the REDMUD researchers were able to provide. At the beginning of the project, the REDMUD researchers (generally speaking) knew the main steps required to achieve their technical objectives – that is, they could draw out an unspecified flow chart detailing the main unit processes required to either extract their target material from bauxite residue, or transform its properties in order to make it suitable for use in construction materials. Beyond this, gaps would begin to appear in their knowledge. For example, they would know that a mineral acid would be required for a certain process, but not which one or what concentration would be required; or that a high temperature would be necessary to achieve a given transformation, but not the exact temperature. These are the gaps that they would aim to fill through their research, both through gaining a greater theoretical understanding of the underlying mechanisms involved, and through exploratory work in the laboratory. As a result, the two main forms of information which

could be obtained from the REDMUD researchers were unspecified flow diagrams, and ‘parameter sets’ describing the process conditions (inputs) and results obtained (outputs) for given experimental setups.

Traditional, commercial LCA software packages, including closed-source, licensed software such as SimaPro [91] and GaBi [103] and open-source alternatives e.g. OpenLCA [92], are designed to allow practitioners to carry out *full LCAs*. These software packages *can* be used to carry out streamlined LCAs, but they are not designed with this task in mind. In addition, there is a steep learning-curve associated with these software packages [104], which effectively restricts their use to *LCA practitioners*, at the exclusion of other interested parties.

Part of my role within the REDMUD project was to foster a greater understanding of life cycle environmental consequences and life cycle assessment approaches in the other researchers in the network. The ultimate achievement to this end would be to get to a point where the other researchers have both the knowledge and, importantly, the tools to carry out their own streamlined assessments, and understand the implications of the results they obtain. Papers III and IV contribute towards this goal.

From a technical perspective, the main deficiency of traditional LCA software with respect to the anticipatory LCA approach was the difficulty of parameterisation. Most LCA software allows flow amounts within a model to be determined by parameters, but the default is to provide a single fixed value. This is important for full LCA, as a single, robust and well referenced value is what is required. For anticipatory LCA however, particularly in situations where *options appraisal* is an important aspect of the study, the ability to quickly set up a base model, and then vary each of the flow amounts assessed using parameters is a more important function. Lcopt (**L**ife **C**ycle **O**ptions appraisal tool), the peer-reviewed software which comprises Paper III, was designed with exactly this consideration in mind.

Lcopt has a different workflow to traditional LCA software. In a typical LCA you would draw a process flow diagram (usually on paper initially) to describe your foreground model; collect data to describe each of the unit processes in the diagram; then, using LCA software, transcribe all of this information into tables describing the inputs and outputs of each unit process. There is typically no easy way to check that the structure of your tables matches that of your initial flow diagram.

The lcopt workflow acknowledges that the process flow diagram is central to LCA modelling. Users draw the unspecified flow diagram directly into the software (Figure 8). Each of the links in the process diagram, representing flows in the LCA model, are automatically assigned parameters. The user can then create any number of parameter sets to describe different process options for analysis. These parameters can either be set directly, or using mathematical formulas. The information in the diagram and the parameter sets is then automatically transformed into a data structure which can be analysed using the open-source LCA calculation package Brightway2 [73].

Figure 8. Lcopt's process flow diagram drawing interface

For example, Figure 9 shows a simple flow chart created using lcopt. This foreground model consists of three unit processes required to make a cup of tea. Parameter sets describing different variations of this process (e.g. black tea, tea with milk, strong tea, weak tea) can be created and the LCA results can be compared (Figure 10, panel a). The flow chart can also be easily updated (for example adding 'sugar'), and the corresponding parameter will be automatically added to each parameter set (with a default value of zero).

Figure 9. Example flow sheet created with Icopt

Figure 10. Example results from Icopt. a) stacked bar chart comparing three different process options. b) 'bulls-eye' chart showing hotspots of impact for a 'milk with one sugar' process option.

Lcopt presents the calculated LCA results in a range of interesting and intuitive ways. These include traditional representations such as stacked bar charts (Figure 10, panel a), pie charts and tables, alongside novel representations, such as the interactive 'bulls-eye' chart, which can be used for hotspot identification (Figure 10, panel b).

Paper IV describes a method to further simplify the LCA modelling process for non-experts. As mentioned above, the LCA workflow typically begins with an LCA flow diagram being drawn on a piece of paper. Paper IV describes a computer vision pipeline which can automatically identify the boxes and links of a hand-drawn process flow diagram in order to generate an LCA model. A *pipeline* in computer programming refers to a sequence of processes in which the output of one becomes the input of the next, akin to a factory production line. This pipeline is implemented in a separate software package called *lcopt-cv*.

Figure 11. Intermediates steps in the computer vision for LCA pipeline. a) original image, b) thresholded image, c) closed image, d) identified contours (boxes in blue), e) boxes identified, f) final processed image

The pipeline begins with loading an image file and converting it to greyscale. The background of the image is equalised in order to account for lighting differences in the photograph, then the foreground of the image – the diagram – is isolated from the background – the paper on which is it drawn – using *thresholding* [105]. Thresholding identifies areas in an image which are darker and lighter than a given *threshold* value (Figure 11, panel b) and converts the input image to a binary output image, consisting only of black and white pixels.

The thresholded image is then *dilated* and *closed* [105](Figure 11, panel c). This is an image processing operation which is used to fill in unintentional gaps in lines. Contours in the image are then detected and simplified, and rectangles (contours with four corners) are identified from the simplified contours as ‘boxes’ (Figure 11, panel d). Spurious boxes are filtered out based on their relative size (e.g. a small box, the second ‘l’ in Alkali, is identified inside the top-rightmost box of Figure 11, panel d, but filtered out in the filtering step (Figure 11, panel e, box 4)).

Links between these boxes are identified, using a flood-filling technique described in detail in Paper IV, to determine the layout of the final model (Figure 11, panel f). Within *lcopt-cv*, the final model can then be reviewed by the user and exported as an *lcopt* model. The user can then add a parameter set and perform LCA calculations immediately from within *lcopt*.

Lcopt was used in Paper V to perform an anticipatory LCA of six different process options for the preparation of inorganic polymers from bauxite residue. The information received from the REDMUD researcher consisted of a description of the process, which was translated into an agreed process flow diagram, and the results of six different trials using different process conditions and mix designs. The most important variables within the process, listed in Table 4, differed between each mix design. This information formed the basis for the parameter sets used in the *lcopt* model.

Table 4. Details of mix designs prepared according to Hertel et al. [16] and assessed in this study (Source: adapted from Paper V, table 1)

Mix Design ID	Pre-fired composition (%wt.)			Firing temperature (°C)	Alkali for activating solution	Liquid to solid ratio	Pressing
	BR (dry)	Carbon	Silica				
11-N-K	100	0	0	1100	K-silicate	0.25	No
11-C-K	98.4	1.6	0	1100	K-silicate	0.25	No
11-CS-K	88.56	1.44	10	1100	K-silicate	0.25	No
12-CS-K	88.56	1.44	10	1200	K-silicate	0.25	No
12-CS-Na	88.56	1.44	10	1200	Na-silicate	0.15	Yes
14-CS-K	88.56	1.44	10	1450	K-silicate	0.25	No

The results of the assessment are presented in section 4.3 below, however the use of anticipatory LCA, modelled using lcopt's fully parameterised approach efficiently yielded important and interesting results about the potential hotspots of environmental impact in this process. Lcopt was also used to calculate the potential net environmental impact of the combined iron extraction/inorganic polymer flow sheet presented as a case study in Paper VI. For the types of assessment required by the REDMUD project, lcopt provides a simplified but useful tool to provide publication quality information. The addition of lcopt-cv promises to make the modelling process even easier in future.

4.3 Single step valorisation of bauxite residue

What are the major life cycle environmental considerations in the creation of inorganic polymers from bauxite residue, a single step valorisation pathway?

Paper V investigates the potential hotspots of environmental impact in the creation of inorganic polymers from bauxite residue. In this process (shown in Figure 12), bauxite residue is mixed with a carbon source (to reduce Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+}) and a silica source (to lower the melting point of the mixture). This precursor mix is then fired in a rotary kiln at a temperature of between 1100 and 1450°C. The precursor is then rapidly cooled and milled to a reactive precursor powder.

The powder is then mixed with an alkaline activating solution, composed of either sodium or potassium silicates, which begins the polymerisation reaction. The mixture is then poured into a block mould, optionally pressed using a hydraulic press, and cured at 60°C for 72 hours. The resulting block, if it has a sufficient compressive strength ($>\sim 40$ MPa), can be used in paving applications. Using anticipatory LCA, the environmental impact of six different mix designs was assessed (detailed in Table 4 above), using the 12 impact categories recommended by the ILCD [74] and the human health NORM impact assessment method developed in Papers I and II.

Figure 12. Generalised process for high BR Inorganic Polymer production (Source: Paper V, figure 2)

The mix designs with no carbon or silica addition, and with just carbon added (both fired at 1100°C), while consistently demonstrating the lowest environmental impact across all categories, did not have sufficient compressive strength for use in paving applications. Within the identical, potassium based mix designs (XX-CS-K in Figure 13) higher impact was correlated with increasing firing temperature.

Figure 13. Relative impact of all six mix designs across the 13 impact categories. In all categories results are normalised to the mix design with the maximum impact in that category, such that the highest impact value is equal to 100%. Categories are ordered by the range between the highest and lowest impact. The shape of the points represents the materials and activating solutions used. Full details of the mix designs described by each of the ID codes are provided in Table 4. 7-day compressive strengths are shown in brackets. Impact categories are abbreviated as follows: AC, terrestrial acidification; FE, freshwater eutrophication; FT, freshwater toxicity; GW, global warming; HT-C, human toxicity - carcinogenic effects; HT-NC, human toxicity - non-carcinogenic effects; IR-A, ionising radiation - artificial radionuclides; IR-N, ionising radiation - NORM (releases to environment); ME, marine eutrophication; OZD, ozone layer depletion; PM, particulate matter formation; POC, photochemical ozone formation; RD, resource depletion. (Source: Paper V, figure 3)

Figure 14. LCA results comparing the 12-CS-K vs 12-CS-Na mix designs. Panel A shows the average contribution to overall impact of the precursor, the activating solution, milling, and other processes (combined) for these two mix designs. Impacts in all three panels are ordered by the contribution of the precursor to the overall impact (descending). Panel B shows the relative impact of blocks produced from the 12-CS-K and 12-CS-Na mix designs. Results for all categories are normalised to the mix design with the maximum impact in that category, such that the highest impact value is equal to 100%. Panel C shows the relative impact of K-silicate and Na-silicate activating solutions. Results for all categories are normalised to the activating solution with the maximum impact in that category, such that the highest impact value is equal to 100%. Impact categories are abbreviated as above. (Source: Paper V, figure 4)

Focusing on the 12-CS-K and 12-CS-Na mix designs, it is clear that there are two major hotspots of environmental impact – creation of the reactive precursor and the activating solution – with milling representing a minor hotspot in some impact categories (Figure 14, panel A). The Na-based mix design has a lower impact in 10 of the 13 impact categories assessed (Figure 14, panel B). This is partly due to the lower impact of Na-silicate solution in comparison to K-silicate solution in most impact categories (Figure 14, panel C) however this does not fully explain the trend seen. The Na-based mix design requires a lower activating solution to precursor ratio, therefore in categories where the precursor has a relatively high contribution to the overall impact (global warming and acidification, Figure 14, panel A), the higher amount of precursor in the mix means that the Na-based mix design has a higher impact than the K-based design in these categories (Figure 14, panel B).

More specific hotspots of impact were identified by focusing on the 12-CS-Na mix design. The bulls-eye charts, shown in Figure 15, reveal that while the production of the precursor and activating solution are hotspots of impact across all categories, the reasons for this, at the next level up, differ between impact categories. For example, while the production and combustion of fuels for the rotary kiln is a major contributor towards the impact of the precursor in all impact categories, for global warming, the direct emission of CO₂ as the added carbon reacts with iron in the rotary kiln also plays a significant role. In the ionising radiation impact category for artificial sources, the electricity required to provide the kiln rotation has a larger impact than the fuels used in the kiln, however when considering ionising radiation impact from NORM the opposite is true. This is mainly due to the release of NORM radionuclides in the mining and combustion of coal.

The identification of potential hotspots of environmental impact at this early stage in the development of the bauxite residue inorganic polymer technology has led to suggestions on how the impact can be reduced without reducing the functional properties of the final product. In the short term, firing the precursor using natural gas, rather than the average fuel mix, offers environmental savings in 12 out of the 13 impact categories (ozone depletion impact increases due to the use of halon fire suppressants in natural gas pipelines).

Figure 15. Hotspot diagrams for 12-CS-Na. These should be read as hierarchical pie charts, as outlined in the top right panel. Each ring represents a level of the system tree, with the arc angle representing the contribution to overall impact (as in a traditional pie chart). Selected hotspots are shown as annotations. In both ionising radiation categories only releases to the environment are considered.

More substantial changes to the process could yield even greater environmental savings. For example, the compressive strength of some of the mix designs far exceeds the ~40 MPa which is required for use in paving applications (up to 149 MPa for 12-CS-Na). This suggests that this precursor could be diluted with 'raw' unreactive bauxite residue while retaining sufficient compressive strength, significantly reducing the environmental impact of the final paving block. Subsequent research has suggested that mixes consisting of just 30% precursor with 70% raw bauxite residue retain sufficient compressive strength to be used in paving applications [106]. In addition, research into alternative firing methods using a microwave furnace has yielded positive early results [107]. The primary energy carrier in this case would be electricity, which could be produced via renewable means.

The results of Paper V demonstrate that the processes required to bring about the valorisation of bauxite residue will necessarily cause environmental impacts. The use of high temperature processes and chemicals, such as sodium and potassium silicate, stand out as the leading causes of these impacts. Reducing the impact incurred by the valorisation process by tackling these hotspots is an important part of ensuring that the valorisation of bauxite residue has a net positive effect on the environment.

4.4 Multi-stage valorisation of bauxite residue

What additional life cycle considerations arise from more complex, multi-stage valorisation pathways for bauxite residue?

Paper V highlighted that the impact incurred during the processing of bauxite residue needs to be reduced as much as is practical in order to maximise the potential for an overall net positive environmental effect through valorisation. This is further formalised in Paper VI, in which more complex, multi-stage valorisation routes are considered.

The most important concept in the assessment of these pathways in Paper VI is that of the overall environmental balance of a valorisation system (Figure 16). When bauxite residue is sent to a valorisation system it is no longer sent to landfill, and as such the impacts associated with this landfill are avoided. In addition, when materials produced by a bauxite residue valorisation system reach the market, they displace the need for these materials to be produced elsewhere in the economy, which in turn avoids the environmental

impact associated with the conventional production of these materials.

Figure 16. Simplified environmental balance from the valorisation of bauxite residue (Source: Paper VI, figure 1)

The need to combine multiple valorisation steps in the processing of bauxite residue has been acknowledged as a way to overcome economic and technical barriers since the 1990s [108]. The same theory applies to environmental impacts. Combining the extraction or production of multiple useful materials has the potential to affect both sides of the environmental balance. Producing more materials will obviously add items to the ‘avoided’ column; however there may also be positive effects on the impact *incurred* through valorisation.

In *sequential* production processes, the process used to extract the first material could be engineered to act as a ‘pre-treatment’ stage for a subsequent extraction process of a second material. For example, one avenue explored by REDMUD researchers is the engineering of slag produced from the smelting of bauxite residue (to

extract iron) to enhance the recovery of scandium and titanium in subsequent leaching processes [109].

Combined production processes may reduce the impact incurred through valorisation even further by using a single process to produce two or more materials. For example changes to the precursor mix prior to the high temperature processing of bauxite residue to inorganic polymer precursors can allow iron to be reduced to a metallic form and extracted from the bauxite residue during this single process.

The major challenge for Paper VI was the lack of finalised quantified flow sheets for many of the potential valorisation stages being developed. However, although the exact environmental balance for a given valorisation route could not be calculated, items could be identified which have the potential to tip the scale in one direction or the other.

For the benefits of avoided products this consisted of a ‘size of the prize’ analysis, in which the theoretical maximum avoided environmental impacts could be calculated based on 100% efficiency of removal of valuable materials from bauxite residue. The results of this analysis are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Theoretical maximum avoided burden for products from 1000 kg of bauxite residue (Source: Paper VI, table 2)

Valorization product	Avoided product/process	Amount avoided (upper limit) kg	Climate change kg CO ₂ eq	Acidification molc H+ eq	Freshwater eutrophication kg P eq	Freshwater ecotoxicity CTUe
(All)	Landfill of BR	1000	8.1	0.08	0.34	67,774
Rare Earth Oxides	Rare Earth Oxides	0.23	6.3	0.04	0.00	103
TiO ₂	TiO ₂	57	325	2.69	0.14	5,610
Al ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	236	327	3.08	0.13	15,911
Iron	Iron	312	553	2.92	0.20	1,900
Inorganic polymer binders	Cement	1000	903	2.10	0.07	1,217
High BR content clinkers	Clinker	1000	976	2.24	0.07	549
Scandium Oxide	Scandium Oxide	0.186	1,127	7.35	0.44	3,539

From a climate change and acidification perspective, scandium oxide is the most valuable target in terms of environmental benefit, followed by cement and clinker, and iron. However, for freshwater eutrophication and particularly for freshwater toxicity, the major

benefit seen is through the avoidance of landfill of bauxite residue, and as such the target of the valorisation route is of less importance.

For the potential impact incurred through valorisation a 'red-flags' analysis was conducted, in which the life cycle environmental impact of materials and processes involved in the proposed flow sheets were calculated, and items with a disproportionately large impact were identified as potential red-flags.

The red-flags fell broadly into four categories: direct emissions from chemical reactions, chemical synthesis, thermal and mechanical energy use.

Reactions including the carbothermic reduction of iron, and the transformation of aluminium oxide into sodium aluminate via soda sintering release carbon dioxide as a reaction product. This has the potential to make a major contribution to the climate change impact of these extraction methods.

Many of the proposed extraction methods for metals from bauxite residue involve the use of chemicals (strong acids, alkalis, ammonium compounds, hydrocarbon solvents) which have high associated environmental impact. Some of these chemicals can be regenerated as part of the process, in which case high recovery levels may abate the potential impact, however due to the alkaline nature of bauxite residue, acids are often consumed via neutralisation reactions which means they cannot be recovered. High acid consumption may represent a significant red-flag.

A noteworthy red-flag within the chemical synthesis category is the proposed use of ionic liquids. Ionic liquids are highly engineered salts which are molten at room temperature. They can act as highly specific solvents for rare earth elements, without the need for water, and without the flammability and low vapour pressure issues associated with organic solvents. However the complex chemical synthesis pathways involved in their production have the potential to cause substantial environmental impact.

The estimated climate change impact per kg of Emim[HSO₄], a candidate ionic liquid for leaching rare earth elements from bauxite residue, based on the method described in Cuéllar-Franca et al. [110] [60], is 5.1 kg CO₂-eq/kg. This is over 30 times higher than the climate change impact per kg of the conventional solvent, sulphuric acid. It is also around 20% of the impact of 1 kg the rare earth oxides it is designed to extract. Efficient recovery of ionic liquid solvents will therefore be vital to ensuring a net environmental benefit from their application, as any losses greater than five grams per gram of metal

oxide recovered automatically result in a net environmental impact, even before the rest of the process is considered.

Thermal energy is an important requirement of valorisation routes where thermodynamically unfavourable chemical reactions need to be driven to completion. These include the production of construction products (cement clinkers and inorganic polymer precursors), as well as the extraction of iron and aluminium. In most current industrial settings, and with current reactor technology, fossil fuels are the most likely source of this thermal energy, and therefore constitute a red-flag for environmental impact. Likewise, mechanical energy, primarily for crushing, grinding and milling of products and intermediates will most likely, in the short to medium term, be provided by electricity generated using fossil fuels.

Paper VI also presents a streamlined LCA case study of a combined flow sheet for which basic quantitative data was available: the simultaneous production of iron and inorganic polymer precursor. This case study validated some of the red-flags identified in the prior analysis (Figure 17). These included direct emissions from chemical reactions (CO_2 from the carbothermic reduction of iron), production of chemicals (boric oxide and sodium silicate), thermal energy (from the smelting process) and mechanical energy (in the rotation of the rotary kiln, milling of the precursor and pressing of the blocks).

In addition however, it also confirms that a combined valorisation process has the potential to lead to a net environmental benefit. Figure 18 shows the environmental balance of the combined iron/inorganic polymer valorisation route, broken down by contributing processes – both incurred impact and avoided impact. For climate change, freshwater eutrophication and freshwater ecotoxicity there is a net environmental benefit. For acidification however there is a net environmental impact, primarily due to the impacts incurred in boric oxide production.

Interestingly, for climate change both the displacement of iron and construction materials are required to shift the balance of the valorisation system over to net benefit (neither of the green bars in Figure 18, panel a, are large enough to cross the y-axis alone). In contrast, for freshwater eutrophication and freshwater ecotoxicity, the avoidance of landfill alone is sufficient to push the valorisation system towards net benefit. This further validates the conclusions of the ‘size of the prize’ analysis for these impact measures.

Figure 17. Bulls eye hotspot diagrams the combined production of iron and inorganic polymer precursor. Selected hotspots are shown as annotations. (Source: Paper VI, figure 4)

a) Climate change

b) Acidification

c) Freshwater eutrophication

d) Freshwater ecotoxicity

Figure 18. Net environmental impact of a combined iron extraction and inorganic polymer synthesis valorisation route for four environmental impact categories, broken down by contributing processes. Red bars indicate incurred impact from valorisation processes, green bars indicate avoided impact through the displacement of products and processes. Total net impact is indicated by the arrow and value on the x-axis. (Source: Paper VI, figure 5)

An understanding of the concept of environmental balance, combined with prior knowledge of the magnitude of the potential environmental impacts of materials and processes is valuable to process engineers as a screening step early in the development of new technologies and techniques. For the REDMUD researchers, knowledge of just a few environmental heuristics based on the red-flags identified here may prompt a deeper consideration of the life cycle environmental impact of the processes they are developing.

This should be followed up by a more detailed assessment, for example a streamlined LCA once basic quantitative data becomes available, which may further direct research into changes to the process to increase the environmental benefit.

Ideally, the anticipatory LCA approach should be integrated into the design process, with further assessments taking place in parallel to the development of the technical aspects of the technology. While this is an aspirational scenario for process engineering in general, incorporating an environmental perspective into the early stages of the training of the REDMUD researchers within this project should foster environmental and life cycle thinking which they can take forward into their careers, and, hopefully, use to good effect.

5 Discussion

In the development of new technologies there is always a temptation to prioritise the technical and short term economic considerations over the environmental. The case of Thomas Midgely Jr., the inventor of both leaded petrol and CFC refrigerants, serves as a stark warning in this regard. Hailed as technological marvels in their day, the phasing out of these damaging substances required both worldwide political action and huge monetary expense.

In the 21st century, strong environmental policies are increasingly becoming a key component of industry's social license to operate. It has therefore never been more important to allow the developers of the next generation of industrial processes to understand the life cycle environmental implications of the technologies they will create.

This thesis contributes to this aspiration for the valorisation of bauxite residue in three ways. Firstly, it is important to include as many of the potentially important impact pathways as is practicable when considering the life cycle impact of new technologies. The successful implementation of the NORM exposure impact assessment method, described in Papers I and II and used in Paper V, allows this important impact to be considered, not only for bauxite residue valorisation, but for all other industrial processes for which it may represent a significant impact.

Secondly, it provides tools to allow both experienced LCA practitioners, and engineers unfamiliar with the intricacies of LCA to perform streamlined assessments of the environmental performance of new technologies. The software packages presented in Papers III and IV are designed to make LCA intuitive and easy for non-experts. This is an important step towards the integration of life-cycle thinking into process design.

Finally, it provides tangible examples of the kinds of environmental considerations which are important in the valorisation of bauxite residue. The anticipatory LCA presented in Paper V highlights key areas of the process for creating inorganic polymers where the environmental impact can be reduced – for example dilution of reactive precursor with unreactive bauxite residue. This has led to new technical research into these areas, which can in turn be followed up with further streamlined assessments of the environmental consequences. This has the potential to ratchet towards a better and better process.

Paper VI demonstrates that even in the absence of quantitative data, life cycle thinking approaches can be used as an important screening step when considering process options for bauxite residue valorisation. The recognition that the overall environmental impact of a valorisation process is a balance between the impact incurred and the impact avoided, combined with even a small amount of knowledge about the environmental implications of possible alternative approaches can help to focus research on important areas. For example, the recognition that if using ionic liquids as solvents, solvent recovery is an important environmental (as well as economic) consideration may enhance research into this particular aspect.

This thesis contributes to the field of LCA in three distinct ways: through the development of new characterisation methods, through the addition of new LCA case studies and applications of life cycle thinking to the literature, and through the development of new LCA foreground modelling software. While I believe each of these contributions are important, their relative importance is an interesting question.

It would be fair to say that the development of new characterisation methods in Papers I and II is the most significant contribution to the *science* of LCA. Despite the proliferation of variants of impact assessment methods, the introduction of a previously unassessed impact measure into the LCA framework is uncommon, and of potential significance to a broad range of future investigations across multiple industries, far beyond the assessment of bauxite residue valorisation.

In terms of the *practice* of LCA however, the development of the lcopt and lcopt-cv software packages in Papers III and IV are arguably a more important contribution, particularly in terms of the number of LCA practitioners who are likely to benefit from the work.

This raises an interesting question as to the value of software as science. Are tools that facilitate scientific discoveries as important as the discoveries themselves? Many scientific fields already have specific ‘methods’ journals⁷, usually for reporting lab protocols or data processing pipelines. But does a new piece of software make the same contribution as a new method?

⁷ For example Nature Methods (ISSN: 1548-7091); Methods in Molecular Biology (ISSN: 1064-3745); Methods in Ecology and Evolution (ISSN: 2041-210X), MethodsX (ISSN: 2215-0161)

In recent years a number of research software journals, such as SoftwareX (ISSN: 2352-7110) and the Journal of Open Source Software (ISSN: 2475-9066), have been created to acknowledge the positive impact that good software has on scientific progress. Works submitted to these journals consist of a short *metaper* providing a description of the software, and a repository containing the software code. The code and the paper are both peer-reviewed, as the *science* of the work is contained within the code. Paper III, describing lcopt, is one such metaper.

Paper IV on the other hand, which describes lcopt-cv, is a *traditional* scientific paper. On the face of it this 7,000 word manuscript contains a lot more *science* than the 192 words in Paper III, however it is important to note that although the source code for lcopt-cv is open for anyone to scrutinise, it has not been officially peer-reviewed. The decision to publish lcopt-cv in this format was taken because of the potential broader interest within the field in the underlying methods employed by the software. I would hold however that Paper III and Paper IV are of equal significance to the LCA literature.

Papers V and VI contribute to the advancement of both the field of LCA and the field of bauxite residue valorisation. From the perspective of bauxite residue valorisation, they are the most significant papers in the thesis. They provide tangible examples of how, with limited and imperfect data, important and actionable conclusions can be drawn with respect to the environmental balance of valorisation pathways. Paper V further provides a case study useful not only in the context of the production of inorganic polymers from bauxite residue, but to the far broader context of the use of industrial wastes as precursors to construction materials.

From the perspective of LCA however, these two papers arguably make the smallest contribution. Paper V demonstrates the application of the LCIA method developed in Papers I and II, and the software developed in Paper III, and adds another potentially useful case study to the growing library of LCA studies. Paper VI provides further evidence that life cycle thinking approaches are useful in of themselves, without the need for a full LCA. The novel red-flags analysis for high level semi-quantitative assessment of unquantified systems is a method which could be usefully applied more broadly.

As with any study, there are limitations to the work presented in this thesis. With regards to the development of the NORM exposure LCIA methods, the most significant limitations are around the uncertainty involved with the complex cause-effect chains required

to be modelled. In addition to modelling uncertainty and parameter uncertainty, this also includes decision rule uncertainty (as described in [111]), with regard to the particular features of the radionuclides involved. Specifically, this type of uncertainty is introduced by the use of value judgements as to how to deal with the inherent uncertainty surrounding the long term behaviour in landfills, and subsequent transformation and potential redistribution in the environment of the radionuclides studied.

These sources of uncertainty surrounding LCIA methods are acknowledged in the modelling of toxicity indicators [111], and are arguably applicable to all LCIA methods. Even robust measures such as climate change impact, where modelling and parameter uncertainty are less significant, are subject to decision rule uncertainty, particularly with regard to the time horizon employed for relative radiative forcing [112] and how to deal with temporary carbon storage [113]. Thus, as with all commonly used LCIA methods, the NORM exposure methods presented here represent the best currently available methods for assessing this previously unassessed metric of environmental impact.

With regards to the software tools presented in this thesis, the main limitation is currently seen in their specificity. These tools were originally designed to perform a specific task, namely modelling relatively straightforward, 'chemical engineering' style systems for which the streamlined assessment of multiple scenarios is desirable. While *lcopt* is potentially more broadly applicable as an LCA foreground modelling software, it may struggle to cope with more complex models, for example those involving internal loops. That said, *lcopt* is undergoing continuing development as part of a growing set of open-source LCA tools and is beginning to build a community of developers and users contributing to its development. The open-source software model provides a good platform for the current limitations of the software to be identified and resolved in a collaborative fashion.

The case studies of valorisation pathways presented in Papers V and VI are, necessarily, based on limited and imperfect information. While the approaches taken were designed to acknowledge and ameliorate the effects of this, the resulting uncertainty because of this fact still persists. The studies set out in these papers should however provide a framework for the future assessment of these valorisation pathways with better data when it becomes available. A further limitation, common to all LCA studies, is that the results and their interpretation are limited only to the particular aspects of

sustainability measured in the study. When using this type of information to support decisions about the most sustainable future direction for the valorisation of bauxite residue, it should of course be considered alongside other issues, including the social and economic implications of the technologies being developed.

6 Conclusions and future work

This thesis represents an important first step towards a comprehensive understanding of the life cycle environmental aspects of bauxite residue valorisation. It demonstrates the importance of considering the environmental impacts which are incurred through the processes required to transform bauxite residue into useful products, alongside the benefits of avoiding landfill and displacing conventionally produced materials.

Valorisation processes are more akin to primary extraction processes than recycling processes. As a result, there is no guarantee that producing a material through waste valorisation will be any easier, cheaper or better for the environment than via the primary production route. From an environmental perspective, this thesis sets out some important considerations.

At the earliest stage, when proposed processes are only at a conceptual level, life cycle thinking approaches can be used to identify important environmental aspects which are likely to arise as the technology is developed. In the case of bauxite residue, knowledge of the direct emissions which result from chemical reaction processes, an understanding of which chemical reagents are likely to have a high environmental impact, and an acknowledgement of processes with high energy requirements are the most important considerations.

There are a relatively large number of different, potentially valuable valorisation routes for bauxite residue. This opens the possibility of synergies between processing routes which can act to improve the environmental balance of the combined process. The engineering of solid residues for use in construction materials is likely to be the simplest and among the most effective of these synergies, particularly where these materials can displace the need for cement production. However, this thesis also demonstrates that the use of residues enriched in natural radionuclides in residential construction materials can create a potentially significant exposure route to humans for ionising radiation. Thus, construction materials used in infrastructural applications may represent a more desirable route for residue derived materials.

As valorisation technologies are developed from theoretical, to bench scale, to pilot scale and on to industrial application, it is important to gain an understanding of the potential environmental

hotspots associated with the specifics of the process. There are often many alternatives at any given stage, thus a streamlined approach to the assessment of different process options from an environmental perspective is extremely valuable in ensuring that the final process is optimised for environmental performance. The hotspots analysis presented in this thesis for the production of inorganic polymers identified high temperature processing and alkali production as important processes in terms of environmental impact. This provided impetus to new avenues of research into alternative heat sources and alkaline liquor recycling in order to optimise this production route.

The tools, approaches and relationships developed through this thesis open up great potential for interesting and valuable future work. As the proposed valorisation processes for bauxite residue continue to develop, increasingly detailed LCA studies, beginning with streamlined assessments, would be of great value. This may begin with the addition of a brief LCA section into technical papers describing the development of novel processing routes.

These assessments are likely to require additional, peripheral work to maximise their usefulness. One key area which would improve the assessment of rare earth element and scandium extraction processes is better data on the environmental impact of ionic liquid production. The variety and complexity of ionic liquids is such that the use of proxy data would lead to highly uncertain LCA results. In the absence of the opportunity to collect primary production data, a systematic application of the method developed by Cuéllar-Franca et al. [110] to a representative range of ionic liquids would be valuable not only for the assessment of solvometallurgical processes, but for other applications of ionic liquids, including carbon capture and storage, pharmaceutical manufacture and novel battery technologies.

A highly desirable endpoint for the valorisation of bauxite residue would be a highly efficient process, integrated within operation of the alumina plant itself. In addition to the synergies offered by combining valorisation routes, further efficiency gains may be possible through the optimisation of aspects of the Bayer process to promote easier valorisation of the resulting residues. An interesting further perspective, would therefore be to assess the combined environmental performance of an alumina plant optimised to produce a number of materials from bauxite ore, rather than an alumina plus 'end of pipe' valorisation solution.

There is no single, simple answer as to what is the best thing to do with bauxite residue. In my view, the future of sustainable bauxite residue management lies in the development and tailoring of site-specific, residue-specific, integrated valorisation processes, backed up by evidence from environmental assessments carried out from a life cycle perspective. It is my sincere hope that the insights presented here, alongside the tools and approaches developed as part of this thesis can make a significant contribution to this aim.

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